

D8.3 Definition of green standards and parameters

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GLOSSARY

CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DMM	Decision-making Model
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of the Action
DSA	Digital Support App
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IIC	International Institute for Conservation of Historic and Artistic works

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IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
OB	Operational Board
OO	Outreach Officer
PHB	Project Handbook
PM	Project Manager
PC	Project Coordinator
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PO	Project Officer (European Commission)
RMQAP	Risk Management & Quality Assurance Plan
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

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Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to report the green definition and parameters for cultural heritage conservation.

This report covers:

- an introduction to the holistic approach undertaken for this work;
- an outline of the policies, frameworks and literature review undertaken;
- reporting on the inputs and feedback moments during development;
- publication of the definitions and parameters and supporting information on the GoGreen website.

Working towards this deliverable included examining the strategies used in other industries, an extensive review of policies, datasets, and conservation literature, and the application of recognized frameworks to identify the key impacts and parameters in conservation. Alongside this research, focused and widespread inputs and feedback were sought from experts in the conservation community and the field at large. This further ensured relevance of the definition and parameters within any professional context, and their transparent legibility for applying into practice. Green conservation definitions and parameters were created which are theoretically well-grounded and can be broadly supported, and which reflect the individuality and complexity of cultural heritage conservation. The hereby developed definitions and parameters were published, alongside supporting information, on a dedicated page on the GoGreen website [here](#).¹

List of contributors

Name	Organisation	Role
Gwendoline Fife (GRF)	Rijksmuseum	Research and report contributor
Julia Wagner (JW)	Rijksmuseum	Research and report contributor
Caitlin Southwick	UvA	Research contributor
Katrien Keune	UvA/Rijksmuseum	Editor/Advisor

¹ <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/>.

1. Introduction

Included within the GoGreen project proposal is the aim to define parameters for green conservation and sector-wide standards. This is specified within Task 8.3 Eliminate Greenwashing in Conservation and Policy Advocacy ‘(...) we will define the parameters and standards for “green conservation” based on the Green Deal and other policy documents and cross-reference these with what we define as critical for achieving green conservation in line with the other work packages, the GoGreen DMM and DSA. These definitions will be refined based on surveys distributed to associations and experts...focus groups to include citizen-science input from the conservation and academic communities.’ Within this context standards therefore references a standardized definition of the critical parameters for green conservation that can be broadly supported and applied.

The deliverable will focus on the technicalities and reporting details involved in the work to achieve this and will present the final outcomes. The outcomes were structured into different sections as follows and published in a dedicated page on the GoGreen website ²:

- The placement of the holistic definition within the context of established frameworks;
- The specific, normative definition of green conservation;
- The operational quantitative and qualitative parameters describing the key aspects in assessing impacts;

Aligning with the Green Heritage Manifesto³ the definition and parameters hereby developed will have a major impact in supporting and promoting green conservation. In the first place they are fundamentally needed to clarify the meaning of green conservation. This is a primary step in enabling the profession to reduce its risks and harmful environmental impacts, and engage in the green transition. The legible definitions and parameters created differentiate and broadly outline the unique characteristics of green conservation within a sustainability framework. The definition and parameters will build awareness about the key factors regarding environmental impacts of conservation decisions, materials and practices across the sector. Progress on this has already been achieved through presentations given at the focus groups meetings held with the community and through other channels as part of this work. Through their publication on the GoGreen website the definitions and parameters will directly provide guidance on greener conservation decision-making and implementations. Through their links in the GoGreen DMM, expression in the GoGreen DSA, and integration within education programs, they will further enable the widespread adoption of green decisions and practices within cultural heritage conservation. The definition and parameters form a base for the GoGreen Digital Support App (DSA) being created, and will provide the foundation for developing industry standards with the professional bodies. Their endorsement by professional associations will support unanimity in defining green conservation and the movement to green conservation as standard practice worldwide.

² Holistic definitions take into account all the interconnected parts, dimensions, and context; normative definitions describe how something should be understood or used; operational definitions specify the procedure or criteria for measuring it.

³<https://gogreenconservation.eu/news/green-heritage-manifesto-the-first-european-manifesto-for-more-sustainable-museums/>

2. Research and feedback

In line with this task an approach combining research and feedback was adopted to ensure that the developed definitions and parameters in GoGreen would be relevant and workable. The aim was to: thoroughly consider the current definitions and usages of green-related terms within cultural heritage conservation; identify the key impact areas of conservation decisions and applications, acknowledging their complexity and variability; and legibly present the parameters for their comprehensive application by conservators.

For collecting, reviewing and assessing definitions and usages of related terms within conservation, a database was created and populated with associated literature, policies and pertinent tools, including those specifically for the field and others potentially applicable. The contents were reviewed, and the methodologies used for creating green definitions in other industries (e.g. building and healthcare⁴) were also examined. Preliminary work highlighted the benefit of identifying the profession's strategic impacts within a sustainability framework. Having identified the strongest links between the sustainable development goals and conservation [illustrated here](#)⁵, further associations could be made considering the pertinent policies and professional guidelines. An initial work-in-progress version of the green definitions and parameters was started from this basis. Applying further frameworks enabled detailing of the associated and quantitative parameters. Recognizing that further quantitative, but also qualitative parameters, are required for conservators in their decisions and applications, the inclusion of other specific considerations regarding the individuality of the object/collection and treatment/decision outcomes could be further elucidated. Combining these gave a work-in-progress list of the green parameters for conservation.

Adjacent to this work, many meetings and consultations were held with colleagues, firstly in the consortium for their expert input, and to cross-reference initial research findings with the factors considered critical for achieving green conservation in line with the other work packages, the GoGreen DMM and DSA. Meetings and consultations were also held with researchers from the other projects in the EU cluster (Moxy and GreenArt), and other external experts in conservation and sustainability. These combined inputs provided invaluable (and positive) feedback and enabled further refining of the definition and parameters. Following this, meetings were opened to the broader community. A version of the definition and parameters was then published on the website, sent to an established external committee, and a survey disseminated within the conservation community for feedback⁶. Further inputs and feedback led to updated versions, with the last published online on the 11th of February 2025.

During the development of the definition and parameters, the associated approach with work-in-progress versions were variously disseminated/published and made widely available. Additionally, until its publication on the GoGreen website a document with the work-in-progress Definition and Parameters of Green Conservation was continually shared on the UvA Research Drive with the consortium and they were informed of major updates.

⁴ e.g. World Green Building Council <https://worldgbc.org/>, <https://practicegreenhealth.org/>, <https://greenhospitals.org/>

⁵ For all the imbedded links in this report, the full URL can be found in section 5. *References* on page 14.

⁶ Described in further detail below.

2.1 Policies, tools, frameworks and literature review

A database was created for collecting resources related to green and environmental terminology in conservation for potential review. This was populated with scientific conservation literature (340 papers), policies (25), forums and websites (30), databases and tools (20), and review categories defined (e.g. 'key words', 'definitions of green and sustainable').

Within the literature resources the titles/abstracts were initially read and a priority assigned based on indicated relevancy. Ultimately, during years 1 and 2 of the project, 304 literature sources were reviewed, the results of which will be detailed in a forthcoming paper. The database, adapted for this publication, will be added to the GoGreen project's online environment on Zenodo (an open access repository). Some screenshots of the database are included in *Appendix I*.

Reviewing these resources was a critical aspect in the work. It helped clarify the scope and the frameworks to be applied, providing an overview of the factors most commonly considered in association with green conservation. A change in focus with respect to the type of sources (e.g. specific testing of new conservation materials, green in museums and cultural heritage in general) indicated the strongly context-dependent and relative significance of any specified factors/parameters.

Database creation: JW. Review categories: JW and GRF. The majority of review work was carried out by: GRF, Anna Turrina (AT), JW. A few were carried out by volunteers Josefa Orrego, Zuraida Akma, Hilde Berteig Rustan, Daniela Molinari. The semantic review analysis was completed by: AT, in discussion with GRF and JW.

2.2 Reporting on Inputs and Feedback

Opportunities for giving input and feedback through surveys and open focus group meetings were advertised via personal contacts, on social media and a signed-up contact list. 230 named contacts thereby contacted included personal contacts, cluster members, conservation suppliers and 160 subscribers who had registered via a Qualtrics sign up form for surveys (134), newsletters (87), focus groups and other initiatives (48). Qualtrics subscribers were migrated to Mailchimp if they have selected to receive newsletters. This platform hosts 175 subscribers in total registered for newsletters (all), surveys (68) and focus groups and other initiatives (74). Selected details on the background of the contacts and potential participants are given in *Appendix II - Contact List Details*.

2.2.1. Online Definition and Parameter Focus Group Meetings

All meetings were generally 1 hour long and held on zoom. Typically, they comprised an introductory presentation from GRF, with at least 30 minutes for feedback and discussion. Generally hosted by GRF with JW. Notes from focus group meetings were added to a growing presentation format which was held on the UvA Research Drive.

Focus Group Meeting open invitations

Conservators, Conservation Scientists and Curators.

Dates: 21_12_2023, 01_02_2024, 08_02_2024, 26_02_2024, 18_03_2024, 22_03_2024, 27_03_2024, 22_04_2024, 13_05_2024, 16_05_2024 (4 separate 1hr long meetings), 22_05_2024, 30_05_2024, (3 separate 1hr long meetings), 18_06_2024, 23_09_2024.

Attendees: *Around 60 in total.*

While participant location was not documented formally, countries known to be represented by attendees: Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, Cyprus, Denmark, Egypt, France, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Mexico, Morocco, Netherlands, Portugal, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, UK, USA.

Meetings with researchers from GoGreen consortium

Consortium workshop (2 hrs).

Date: 16_06_2023.

Attendees: *Aida Kalender, Antanas Melinis, Caitlin Southwick, Clare Richardson, Edith Joseph Francesca Ramacciotti, Petrasz Patrycja Janina, Wu Qing, Roberta Zanini, Austin Nevin, David Thickett, Silvia Prati, Maartje Stols-Witlox, Joel Taylor, Loic Bertrand, Sander van Lith, Han Zhou, Katrien Keune plus others in consortium (invitation shared via gogreenwpleads@list.uva.nl).*

Regular Meetings.

Individual meetings with *David Thickett, Maartje Stols-Witlox, Joel Taylor.*

Attendance of WP2, WP3, WP4 by GRF in years 1 and 2 where the topic was discussed.

Attendance of bimonthly WP6 meetings by GRF and JW in years 1 and 2, for critical association of resources, parameters, and frameworks in the GoGreen DSA.

Meetings with selected researchers from GoGreen Cluster projects Moxy and GreenArt

Invitations were sent via the respective project coordinators.

Dates: 07_09_2023, 25_09_2023, 9_10_2023, 15_01_2024, 18_01_2024, 25_01_2024, 11_04_2024, 6_05_2024.

Attendees: *Anton Nikiforov, Caitlin Southwick, Aistè Galaunytė, Julia Wagner, Piero Baglioni, Dieuwertje Schrijvers, Ilaria Bonaduce, Silvia Pizzimenti, Alex Zabeo, David Chelazzi, Michaela Florescu, Josephine Bobeck, Giovanna Poggi, Abdelrazek Elnaggar, Matija Strlič.*

Material Suppliers, Individual external experts, and Professional Association representatives

Dates: 10_01_2023, 24_08_2023, 28_10_2023, 22_02_2024, 06_05_2024, 18_06_2024, 13_08_2024, 27_08_2024, 9_10_2024.

Attendees: Sarah Stannage, Lorraine Finch, Sarah Nunberg, Johann Deffner, Amanda Rose, Joy Manna, Kim Kraczon, Matthew Eckelman (multiple meetings).

Regular external collaborators

Collaboration with Anna Turrina and Davide Del Curto (Politecnico di Milano, Department of Architecture and Urban Studies, Milan) was established on 23_10_2023. From 12_2023 until 02_2025 regular bimonthly meetings were held between GRF, AT and JW.

Webinar WP8

Date: 30_05_2024.

Webinar IIC Innovative Scholars

Invitations sent via IIC to their 32 Innovative Scholars. Hosted on Zoom by Marina Herriges.

Date: 08_11_2024.

Attendees: Marina Herriges, David Thickett and 33 other attendees.

Country: Location of attendees not recorded, but known to include India, and various countries in Africa and South America.

Conference Virtual Hub

Virtual hub at International Institute for Conservation of historic and artistic works congress, Sustainable Solutions for Conservation: New Strategies for New Times, 23 to 27 September 2024, virtual hub presentation and discussion, 23_09_2024.

Upcoming

IIC Fellows Meeting 24_04_2025.

2.2.2 Surveys

Two surveys were carried out in relation to input and feedback on the work for this deliverable. The first - Tools for Greener Conservation - provided input from the community on the critical factors in green conservation, also of direct relevance for the GoGreen DSA. The survey results were implemented in the construction of the parameters. See *Appendix III - Tools for Greener Conservation*. The second survey - Definition and Parameters Feedback (which is ongoing) - was constructed to evaluate agreement, clarity and relevance of definition and parameters.

Overall results have been overwhelmingly positive for agreement, clarity and relevance- see Appendix IV - Definition and Parameters Feedback. Critical comments and suggestions were considered and integrated in the definition and parameters as described further below.

2.2.3 Written Distribution and Feedback

Until its publication on the GoGreen website a document with the work-in-progress Definition and Parameters of Green Conservation was continually shared on the UvA Research Drive with the consortium and they were informed of major updates. This document underwent five major adapting moments during years 2 and 3 in accordance with the continued research review findings and inputs/feedback discussed above. Thoughtful and key feedback was provided therein.

A work-in-progress document was shared with the coordinators of the cluster projects Moxy and GreenArt for written feedback 06_2024. Positive reactions, some discussion points, and very useful suggestions were provided. The suggestions were incorporated into the first version of the definitions and parameters published on the website see *Appendix V - GoGreen_definition and parameters_29_08_24*. Further emails were sent to the cluster with a link to the dedicated webpage (with survey links), informing them of updates and kindly requesting written feedback. A further email informing of the updated version on the website and request for feedback was sent on 06_12_2024. Some additional perspectives and very positive responses on the work were received, alongside agreement to share the survey links.

Ten external, knowledgeable and respected conservators and conservation scientists were invited to the 'GoGreen 'Definition and Parameters External Committee': Bronwyn Ormsby, Cecil Krarup Andersen, David Saunders, Ellen Pearlstein, Eric Breitung, Jane Henderson, Johnathan Ashley Smith, Julian Bickersteth, Justine Wuebold, Lorraine Finch. This committee was first sent a written draft definition document (see *Appendix VI - GoGreen_definition and parameters_29_08_24* with dedicated webpage links see below), on 09_09_2024 with a requested deadline for feedback 21_10_2024. The responses were very positive with detailed and insightful feedback, which were collected (separately for the definitions sections and for the parameters), and reviewed sentence by sentence. An accordingly updated version of the definitions section was sent on 08_11_2024 and a version with greater detailing of the parameters, additional background information and the infographic was sent on 31_01_2025. See *Appendix VII - GoGreen_definition and parameters_31_01_25*. In response overwhelmingly positive support for the work and outputs has been received.

The vast majority of comments from combined feedback (i.e. including free text responses in survey) were in broad alignment with one another and the research findings and could be incorporated in the definitions and parameter descriptions. Suggestions for expansion/missing aspects were generally in good accordance with one another, but there were occasionally contradictions. For example, whilst it was suggested by some to add a weighting to the parameters/identify big impact items as against small impact items, others noted that since relative impacts are highly context driven, a weighting could be misleading and further inadvertently reduce agency for the reader. In these situations, the suggestion was not integrated or expressed directly in the definition and parameters but addressed in the supporting information (discussed below).

3. Publication of the Green Definition and Parameters on the GoGreen website

A first version of the one-pager with definitions and parameters for green conservation was published on a dedicated page on the GoGreen website on 29_08_2024 see *Appendix V - GoGreen_definition and parameters_29_08_24*. This was updated twice and last updated on 06_02_2024 with the final [definition one-pager](#) (Figure 1).

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From all the research and feedback there were of course a few outstanding aspects, questions or perspectives that could not be fully or directly resolved within the definitions and parameter descriptions themselves. It was therefore decided to include, answer or otherwise acknowledge these in supporting and background information on the GoGreen website page. On the website page the aim was to structure the work generated in this deliverable to be digestible, adaptable to the reader's interest, and empower direct enactment of the definition and parameters.

Included on GoGreen's 'Defining Green Conservation' page:

The downloadable [definition one-pager](#);

The [work in Progress Definition](#);

A guide to [using the parameters](#);

Information on [the parameters in further detail](#);

Background on the [concept, goal and scope](#), [frameworks considered](#) (with links to the most critical), and overview of [the approach taken](#) in developing the definitions and parameters;

An [acknowledgment](#) of the complexity involved and [further work](#) (with space for an FAQ section under development based on commonly raised comments and questions in the feedback);

And a section for the feedback, acknowledging the [external expert committee](#), and including [the ongoing survey](#).

Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices

Work in progress definition / 06.02.2025

green
conservation

- ...is comparative and contextual
- ...aligns with professional ethics
- ...protects **cultural heritage**
- ...is holistic balanced decision-making
- ...reduces health hazards
- ...benefits **human health and well being**
- ...is accessible
- ...reduces environmental hazards
- ...reduces impacts on the **natural environment & climate change**
- ...is embedded in sustainability
- ...aligns with the circular economy
- ...reduces impacts on **resources**

Holistic Definition for Cultural Heritage Conservation

Conservation has a uniquely positive and powerful role to play in shaping a sustainable future: it preserves cultural heritage for current and future generations and supports economic and societal stability. Climate change and its destructive impacts endangers cultural heritage. So a vital part of cultural heritage conservation is assessing and adapting professional practices to help combat these foremost agents of change. Embedded within this sustainability context, green conservation prioritizes the environment, and human health and wellbeing, through holistic decision-making. Aligned with conservation ethics and values, it allows for future developments and considers the entirety of consequences within investigative, interventive and preventive practice. It involves a considered balancing of the impacts, before, during and after any decision or approach. Cultural heritage professionals should actively adopt a green conservation approach, with institutional support in accordance with the Economic, Social and Environmental pillars of sustainability.

Green Conservation

Green conservation is an aspirational, consultative process and always comparative in practice. A green conservation approach is minimally harmful to the environment and humans. Aligning with the circular economy, green conservation is decarbonizing, zero-waste, accessible, and available. Green conservation is achieved through decision-making and evolving practice, which takes all these aspects into consideration in balance with professional guidelines, and current and continuing research. Green conservation practices encompass the decisions made within the context of collection management and storage, any investigative, preventive or interventive measure, their documentation, the materials used, the frequency of treatment and long-term impacts. Green conservation reinforces and furthers the positive role of conservation in the sustainability of our culture.

Green Parameters

descriptors for green conservation (see website for details)

Hazard impacts on human and environment	G1	Toxicity and hazard metrics for the natural environment
	G2	Toxicity and hazard metrics for humans
Impacts on climate change	G3	Energy – Indoor climate control impacts
	G4	Energy – Consumption in approach / application
	G5	Energy – Conservation approach / treatment-associated materials / products to be used
Impacts on resources	G6	Availability – water & resource use
	G7	Availability – Biodiversity impacts
	G8	Waste
Art work, cultural heritage object specific/ professional parameters	G9	Material / product selection and application method
	G10	Efficiency – Number of applications / consumption / quantities of materials / products used
	G11	Longevity of result
	G12	Accessibility – Availability of approach / used materials / products
	G13	Accessibility – Ease of use and time
	G14	Quality / value impacts of result in meeting preservation goals

**The content of this publication has not been approved by the United Nations and does not reflect the views of the United Nations or its officials or Member States.*

Want to know more?
gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation
info-gogreen@uva.nl

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Figure 1: GoGreen one-pager on Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices.

4. Conclusions

Based on the broad and specific feedback it is concluded that green definitions and parameters were created which reflect the individuality and complexity of cultural heritage conservation. Conceptually aligned with the circular economy and a scientific attitude, the definition and parameters differentiate and broadly outline the unique characteristics of green conservation from a sustainability perspective. The definition and parameters are aspirational and intended for guiding clearer evaluations of 'green conservation' in all aspects and disciplines within cultural heritage conservation, encouraging the use of reliable and comparable data where possible. It is acknowledged that the associated assessments are highly complex, and not all future developments and socio-economic contexts can be foreseen. But the depth and breadth of this research helps ensure that this work offers a valuable and welcome framework that can be immediately used for implementation strategies, graphical schemes and messages.

5. References

Link to published GoGreen Database: upcoming on Zenodo.

[definition one-pager](https://gogreenconservation.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/GoGreen_definition-and-parameters_06.02.2025.pdf): https://gogreenconservation.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/GoGreen_definition-and-parameters_06.02.2025.pdf

[work in Progress Definition](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#definition): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#definition>

[using the parameters](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#USING-THE-GREEN-PARAMETERS): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#USING-THE-GREEN-PARAMETERS>

[the parameters in further detail](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#parameters-in-detail): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#parameters-in-detail>

[concept, goal and scope](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#concept-goal-scope): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#concept-goal-scope>

[frameworks considered](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#frameworks): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#frameworks>

[the approach taken](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#approach): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#approach>

[acknowledgment](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#disclaimer): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#disclaimer>

[further work](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#further-work): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#further-work>

[external expert committee](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#experts): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#experts>

[the ongoing survey](https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#your-feedback): <https://gogreenconservation.eu/defining-green-conservation/#your-feedback>

6. Appendices

Appendix I - Screenshots of Database

Appendix II - Contact Detail List

Appendix III - Tools for Greener Conservation Survey

Appendix IV - Definition and Parameters Feedback Survey

Appendix V - GoGreen_definition and parameters_ 29_08_24

Appendix VI - GoGreen_definition and parameters_ 31_01_25

Appendix VII - GoGreen_definition and parameters_ 06_02_25

Appendix I - Screenshots of Database

Status	Priority 1 high 2 middling 3 low	Year	Author(s)	Title	Publication
Optional	3	2012	Devi Kausar	Sustainability in the Management of World Cultural Heritage	Visions for Global Tourism Industry - Creating and Sustaining
Read	1	2023	Menegaldo M., et al.	Environmental and economic sustainability in cultural heritage	Cleaner Environmental Systems, Volume 9, June 2023, 100124
Read	1	2019	(eds) Walter Leal Filho,	Addressing the Challenges in Communicating Climate Change	Climate Change Management, Springer
Read	1	2019	Semenzin, E., Giubliato, E.,	Guiding the development of sustainable nano-enabled products for	Environ Sci Pollut Res 26, 26146–26158
Read	2	2022	Karimi, F.; Valibeig, N.;	Sustainability Rating Systems for Historic Buildings: A Systematic	Sustainability 2022, 14(19), 12448
Read	1	2017	Tomasetta, C.	The Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment Approach Applied to	Unpublished thesis: DREAMT, Doctorate in Economics and
Read	2	2023	David Thickett, Paul	Assessing and predicting sustainability for maintaining silver	ICOM CC Valencia
Read	1	2023	Davide Del Curto and Anna	Towards a Reasoned Glossary of Green Conservation: A	MDPI, Sustainability 2023, 15(16), 12104;
Read	1	2022	D. Saunders	A Methodology for Modelling Preservation, Access and	Studies in Conservation 67, no. sup1 (2022): 245-252.
Read	1	2016	Balliana, E., Ricci Giulia.,	Assessing the value of green conservation for cultural heritage;	International Journal of Conservation Science Volume 7, Special
Read	1	2016	Chiara Samori, Paola Galletti,	The Green Attitude in Art Conservation:	ChemistrySelect 2016, 1, 4502 – 4508
Read	1	2021	Yiming Jia, Giorgia Sciutto,	Deep eutectic solvent and agar: a new green gel to remove	Journal of Cultural Heritage 51, 2021, 138-144
Read	1	2011	De Silva, Megan, and Jane	'Sustainability in conservation practice.'	Journal of the Institute of Conservation 34, no. 1
Read	1	2011	Sarah Staniforth	'Sustainability and collections'	Conservation perspectives: The GCI Newsletter, Spring 2011:
Read	1	2015	Sarah Sutton	Environmental sustainability at historic sites and museums	Lanham, Maryland : Rowman & Littlefield
Read	2	2022	Velios, Athanasios, and	Linked Conservation Data: Driving Change in Documentation	Studies in Conservation 67, no. sup1 (2022): 293-300.
Read	1	2023	David Saunders	AGM 2023 Talk: the museum environment in an era of sustainability	IIC
Read	1	2010	Sarah Staniforth	'Slow Conservation'	Studies in Conservation. Vol. 55, No. 2, 60 YEARS OF IIC
Read	1	2010	Silence, P.	'How are US Conservators Going Green?: Results of Polling AIC	Studies in Conservation: The journal of the international institute
Read	1	1998	Anastas, P. T., and J. C.	'12 Principles of Green Chemistry - American Chemical Society'	Green Chemistry: Theory and Practice. Oxford University Press,
Read	1	2016	Prat, D., A. Wells, J. Hayler,	'CHEM21 Selection Guide of Classical- and Less Classical-Solvents'	Green Chem. 18, no. 1: 288-96
Read	1	2016	Byrne, F.P., S. Jin, G.	'Tools and Techniques for Solvent Selection: Green Solvent	Sustainable Chemical Processes 4, no. 1: 7
Read	1	2015	Welton, T.	'Solvents and Sustainable Chemistry'	Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and
Read	1	2013	Prat, D., O. Pardigon, H.W.	'Sanofi's Solvent Selection Guide: A Step Toward More Sustainable	Organic Process Research and Development 17, no. 12: 1517-25
Read	2	2009	GlaxoSmithKline	'GSK Solvent Selection Guide'	The Royal Society of Chemistry
Read	2	2009	Alan Phenix	'Some Reflections on the Use of Organic Solvents in Conservation'	AIC News, March 2009 Vol. 34, No. 2
Read	2	2007	Christian Capello, Ulrich	'What is a Green Solvent? A Comprehensive Framework for the	Green Chemistry 9
Read	1	2016	Nunberg, Sarah, Eckelman,	Life Cycle Assessments of Loans and Exhibitions: Three Case	Journal of the American Institute for Conservation, Volume 55,
Read	1	2021	Potts, A. (ICOMOS)	European Cultural Heritage Green Paper Executive Summary	Europa Nostra, The Hague & Brussels.
Read	1	2018	Pagliarino, Amanda	'Environmental Guidelines - An Australian Perspective'	AICCM Bulletin, Volume 39, 2018 - Issue 1
Read	3	2017	Pilar Bosch-Roig, Jose Luis	'Biocleaning of wall paintings on uneven surfaces with warm agar	Gels in Conservation
Read	3	2017	Stavroula Rapli, Stamatis	'Removing iron stains from wood and textile objects: assessing	Gels in Conservation
Read	1	2017	Yana van Dyke	Agarose-enzyme gels in paper conservation	Gels in Conservation
Read	1	2017	Wolbers, R.C.	'Gels, green chemistry, gurus and guides'	Gels in Conservation
Read	1	2017	Volpi, F., et al.	From biomass to restoration: a new green tool for the cleaning of	Gels in Conservation
Read	3	2017	Misa Tamura, Koji Takagi	'Towards the sustainable use of agar/agarose in conservation: a	Gels in Conservation
Read	3	2017	Zarah Walsh-Korb, Soraya	'Responsive bio-based gels for the preservation and treatment of	Gels in Conservation
Read	3	2017	Richard Wolbers	'Terminology and properties of selected gels'	Gels in Conservation
Read	2	2019	Ukko, Juhani, Minna Saunila,	'Sustainable development: Implications and definition for open	Sustainable Development 27, no. 3 (2019): 321-336.
Read	1	2015	Owens, Katharine A., and	'What do we say when we talk about sustainability? Analyzing	International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education (2015).
Read	1	2014	Royce A. Francis, Cassandra	Decision-Analytic Approach for Water Sustainability Definition: A	Journal of Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis 21, no. 3-4 (2014):
Read	1	2017	Moore, Julia E., Alekhyia	Developing a comprehensive definition of sustainability.	Implementation Science 12, no. 1 (2017): 1-8.
Read	1	2012	Abbey, Heidi N.	The green archivist: a primer for adopting affordable,	Archival Issues (2012): 91-115.
Read	1+	2009	Sarah Brophy and Elizabeth	The Green Museum—A Primer on Environmental Practice	(MD, USA: Alta Mira Press, 2009).
Read	1	2012	ECHA Europäische	'Guidance on REACH'	
Read	2	2001	Bergin, M., and A. Russell	'The Environmental Fate and Movement of Organic Solvents in	Environmental Impact of Solvents, 1150-1200
Optional	2	2001	Roy, W.R.	'The environmental fate and movement of organic solvents in water, s	Handbook of Solvents 3 (2001): 1149-2000.
Read	2	2023	C. Hanson	Green Solvents	Hanson Solubility Parameters
Read	1	2021	Marta Guedão, Rui Bordalo,	Available green conservation methodologies for the cleaning of	
Read	1	2022	Marco Valente Chavez	Deep eutectic solvents: green solvents for the removal of degraded	Heritage Science (2022) 10:114
Read	2	2021	Cláudio Correia Fernandes,	Evaluation of Deep Eutectic Systems as an Alternative to Solvents in	ACS Sustainable Chem. Eng. 2021, 9, 15451–15460
Read	1	2018	Albert M.T., Bandarin F.,	Going Beyond: Perceptions of Sustainability in Heritage Studies No.	Heritage Studies Series, vol.5, Springer International Publishing
Read	1	2012	Ford, Patricia Herzog, Peter	IPI's guide to sustainable preservation practices for managing	https://store.imagepermanenceinstitute.org/sustainable-preservati
Read	1	2017	Keitumetse, Susan O.	Perceptions of Sustainability in Heritage Studies	319-323. https://doi.org/10.1080/13505033.2017.1378535 (book
To be acquired	1	2015	Albert, Marie-Theres	Perceptions of sustainability in heritage studies	Vol. 4. Walter de Gruyter GmbH & Co KG, 2015.
Read	1	2021	Rebecca Rushfield	Stemming the tide : global strategies for sustaining cultural heritage	https://smithsonianfigshare.com/articles/book/Stemming_the_Tide
Read	1	2007	Johnston, Paul, Mark Everard,	Reclaiming the definition of sustainability.	Environmental science and pollution research international 14, no.
Optional	3	2017	Sven Pastoors	Towards sustainable innovation : a five step approach to sustainable	Tectum Wissenschaftsverlag, Baden-Baden : Tectum Verlag, 2017
Read	1	2021	Grigoroudis, Evangelos ;	Energy sustainability: a definition and assessment model	Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg
Read	1	2018	Xiaohong Li	Industrial Ecology and Industry Symbiosis for Environmental	Cham : Springer International Publishing : Imprint: Palgrave Pivot,
Optional	3	2020	Urdan, Matthew S. ; Luoma,	Designing Effective Sustainability Assignments: How and Why	Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications
Optional	2	2021	Faulkner, James ; Lu, Liuxing ;	Archivists' golden egg: environmental sustainability practices of	BINGLEY: Emerald Publishing Limited
Optional	2	2018	Blades, N., K. Lithgow, S.	Conservation Heating 24 Years on	Studies in Conservation 63 (1): 15–21
Read	1	2020	Henderson, J.	Beyond Lifetimes: Who do we Exclude When we Keep Things for the	Journal of the Institute of Conservation 43 (3): 195–212
Optional	2	2014	Kirby Atkinson, J.	Environmental Conditions for the Safeguarding of Collections: A	Studies in Conservation 59 (4): 205–212, 2014
Optional	3	2008	Lithgow, K., S. Staniforth, and	Prioritizing Access in the Conservation of National Trust Collections	Studies in Conservation 53 (1): 178–185, 2008
Read	1	2008	NMDC	NMDC Guiding Principles for Reducing Museums' Carbon Footprint	NMDC.London: National Museum Directors' Council
Optional	3	2007	Padfield, T., and K.	Museum Microclimates	Contributions to the Copenhagen conference 19–23 November
Read	1	2013	Padfield, J., S. Vandyke, and	Improving our Environment.	London: National Gallery
Optional	3	2017	Ræder Knudsen, L., and S.	Performance of Danish Low-Energy Museum Storage Buildings	In ICOM-CC 18th Triennial Conference Preprint Copenhagen, ed.
Not accessible	2	2022	David Saunders	Sustainability in Museum Lighting	https://www.icom.org.uk/resource/sustainable-museum-lighting-q-a

Status	Priority	Year	Author(s)	Title	Publication
Optional	3	2021	Taylor, J., M. Lukowski, and L.	Increasing Evidence-Based Decision-Making for Loan Agreements	In ICOM-CC 19th Triennial Conference Preprints Beijing, ed. J.
Read	1	2023	Taylor, Joel, Michael C. Henry,	Managing Collection Environments: Technical Notes and Guidance.	Los Angeles: Getty Conservation Institute.
Optional	3	2015	Antonino Cosentino	Book of Abstracts Colours 2015: Innovative and Sustainable	BOOK OF ABSTRACTS, COLOURS 2015, BRIDGING SCIENCE
Read	1	2014	Rachael Arenstein	GREEN MUSEUMS: A LEED Primer for Preservation, Professionals	GCI Perspectives, Collection Environments Issue, Fall 2014
Reading	1	2019	Ana Galán-Pérez	Preventive conservation and sustainability of heritage collections in	Book of Abstracts. 3rd International Conference in Green
Read	1	2017	Pearlstein, Ellen	Teaching sustainable collection care	Journal of the American Institute for Conservation 56, no. 2
Optional	2	2007	A. Collete	Case Studies on Climate Change and World Heritage	(France: UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 2007)
Optional	3	2000	Barry Kaye, David	'Supercritical Drying: A New Method for Conserving Waterlogged	Studies in Conservation 45 (2000): 233–62.
Optional	2	2022	Buring, Liselotte	Cultural heritage buildings in the circular transition	MA thesis, Utrecht University
Read	1	2017	Nocca, Francesca	The Role of Cultural Heritage in Sustainable Development:	Sustainability 9, no. 10 (2017): 1882.
Read	1	2020	Holden Langemark, Ida	Perspectives on Sustainability in Cultural Heritage Conservation	Gothenburg University
Read	1	2004	Stubbs, Michael	Heritage-sustainability: developing a methodology for the	Planning Practice & Research 19, no. 3 (2004): 285-305.
Read	1	2011	Pollock-Ellwand, Nancy	Common ground and shared frontiers in heritage conservation and	International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology
Optional	3	2021	Baglioni, Piero, and David	How Science Can Contribute to the Remedial Conservation of	Chemistry—A European Journal 27, no. 42 (2021): 10798-10806.
Read	1	2006	Gražulevičiūtė, Indrė	Cultural heritage in the context of sustainable development	Environmental Research, Engineering & Management 37, no. 3
Read	1	2021	Di Turo, Francesca, and Laura	How green possibilities can help in a future sustainable	Sustainability 13, no. 7 (2021): 3609.
Read	1	2021	Lorentz Center	Short summary: Green Conservation Materials for European	Lorentz Center @Snellius
Read	1	2024	Abdelrazek Elinaggar	'Nine principles of green heritage science: life cycle assessment as a	Heritage Science 12
Read	1	2022	Pagliari, Amanda	Climate Change, Climate Action and Cultural Heritage Collections in	Studies in Conservation 67, no. sup1 (2022): 209-218.
Optional	2	2022	Thickett, David.	Better Use of Showcases for Preservation and Sustainability	Studies in Conservation 67, no. sup1 (2022): 267-276.
Read	2	2022	Wuebold, Justine, Ellen	Preliminary Research into Education for Sustainability in Cultural	Studies in Conservation 67, no. sup1 (2022): 326-333.
Read	1	2023	A. Mirabile	Museums and Sustainable Development: a debate without borders	AMA NEWSLETTER, 344, 19 January 2023, p. 78-80
Read	1	2020	Francesca Guiducci, Tracey	Finding Sustainability in the Desert: Conservation of the	IIC Edinburgh Congress 2020
Read	1	2020	Gonçalves, Joana, Ricardo	Contributions to a revised definition of sustainable conservation	TU Delft conference publication
Read	1	2022	Shehata, A. O., Megahed, N.	(3Ts) Green conservation framework: A hierarchical-based	Building and Environment, 224, 109523.
Read	1 +	2021	Neil Winterton	Chemistry for Sustainable Technologies: A Foundation: Edition 2	
Optional	2	2007	E. Carretti, R. Giorgi, D. Berti,	Oil-in-water nanocontainers as low environmental impact cleaning	Langmuir, 23 (11), 2007, pp. 6396-6403.
Not accessible	2	2015	National Research Council	Green Conservation of Cultural Heritage in Rome, October 2015	Conference website
Read	1	2014	A. Macchia, F. Sacco, S.	Chemical exposure in Cultural Heritage restoration: questionnairre	Scienza e Beni Culturali XXX, Quale sostenibilita' per il restauro?,
Not accessible	1	2018	IIC , International Institute for	'Friday, Session 16: Sustainability'	Preventive conservation : the state of the art : contributions to the
Reading	2	2017	Canadian Centre for	'What is a LD50 and LC50?: OSH Answers'	
Read	4 2	2014	Brimblecombe, Peter	Refining climate change threats to heritage	Journal of the Institute of Conservation, Volume 37, 2014 - Issue 2
Reading	2	2013	Yarsan, E., and M. Yipe	'The Important Terms of Marine Pollution "Biomarkers and	Journal of Molecular Biomarkers & Diagnosis S1: 3
Read	1	2013	Ekins, S., A.M. Clark, and A.J.	'Incorporating Green Chemistry Concepts into Mobile Chemistry	ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering 1, no. 1: 8-13
Reading	2	2012	EnviroSIM	'Annex: Modelling as a Tool for Wastewater Treatment Optimisation,	ACEDP Lake Tai Water Pollution Treatment Project
Not accessible	2	2011	International Council of	'Global Product Strategy, ICCA Guidance on Chemical Risk	
Optional	2	2010	Picot, A., and N. Palmade-Le	'Le produit chimique : un outil courant dans le domaine de la	Proceedings of the colloquium «Conservation-Restauration et
Optional	2	2009	Barbaro, S., Raimondi, T.	'Activity of the CIRIAS as regards energy and environment'	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 9
Read	1	2009	Garrard, G.	'Ecocriticism: The ability to investigate cultural artefacts from an	Stibbe, A. (Ed.). The Handbook of Sustainability Literacy: Skills for
Read	1	2008	Saunders, David	Climate Change and Museum Collections	Studies in Conservation (2008) 53
Not accessible	1	2008	Tedone, Melissa, Karen	From gray areas to green areas: developing sustainable practices in	Kilgarrin Center for Preservation of the Cultural Record, School of
Read	1	2007	Elizabeth Pye and Dean Sully	'Evolving Challenges, Developing Skills'	The Conservator 30
Optional	2	2005	Kerski, J., Ross, S.	The essentials of... The Environment.	London: Hodder Arnold
Optional	2	2002	Moncada lo Giudice, G.	'On sustainable development problems, also according to the world	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 2
Optional	2	2002	Pickard, R.	European Cultural Heritage Volume II: A review of Policies and	Strasbourg: Council of Europe
To be acquired	1	1997	Mackenzie, D.	Green Design: Design for the Environment, 2nd ed.	London: Laurence King
Optional	2	1990	Rossmore, H.W.	'Biodegradation and Biodegradation 8'	International Biodegradation and Biodegradation Symposium,
Optional	2		David Suzuki Foundation	' "The Dirty Dozen" Cosmetic Chemicals to Avoid'	
Not accessible	1		Christina Brooks and Dana	'A Green Guide to Sustainable Practice in Conservation'	(paper presented at Going Green)
Optional	2	2018	Clean Link	'What Are Biobased Solvents?'	
Optional	2	2014	Chemat, F., Vian M. A.	Alternative solvents for Natural Products Extraction	Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg
Not accessible	1	2013	Picot, A., and F. Montandon	'Ecotoxicochimie des hydrocarbures' (Ecotoxicochimie of	Lavoisier
Optional	3	2013	Kim, Y.W., M.J. Kim, B.Y.	'Safety Evaluation and Risk Assessment of DLimonene'	Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health - Part B: Critical
Optional	3	2012	Hirota R., H. Nakamura, S.A.	'Limonene Inhalation Reduces Allergic Airway Inflammation In	Inhalation Toxicology 24, no. 6: 373-81
Optional	3	2012	Chemat, S., V. Tomao, and F.	'Limonene as Green Solvent for Extraction of Natural Products'	Environmental Impact of Solvents, 1150-1200
Optional	3	2011	Jessop, P. G.	'Searching for Green Solvents'	Green Chemistry, 2011, 13
Optional	3	2011	Petrosyan, V. S.	'Chemical safety problems'	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 11
Optional	2	2010	Palmade-Le Dantec, N., Picot,	'The prevention of risk: the replacement of toxic solvents less toxic	Actes du colloque <>, 3-5 February 2010
Optional	3	2009	D. Kaya	'D-Limonene'	
Read	1	2002	Lange, J. P.	'Sustainable development: efficiency and recycling in chemicals	Green Chemistry, Issue 6
Optional	3	1999	Curzons, A.D., D.C.	'Solvent Selection Guide: A Guide to the Integration of	Clean Products and Processes 1, no. 2: 82-90
Optional	2	1998	Filippson, A.F., J. Bard, and S.	'Concise International Chemical Assessment Document 5:	World Health Organization, Geneva, 1-32
Optional	2		Julia Barton and Rachel Swift	'The Big Ban: Preliminary Research into Finding a Non-toxic	(paper presented at Green)
Read	1	2020	CHRISTOPHER GARTHE	Sustainability Management in Museums: A new Approach to	
Read	1	2019	H.A. McGhie	Museums and the Sustainable Development Goals: a how-to guide	Curating Tomorrow, UK
Read	1	2019	Historic England	Responses to Climate Change	Historic England
Optional	2	2018	K. Holl, R. Kilian, L. Klemm, K.	Sustainable Museum Storage Buildings for Long-term Preservation	Studies in Conservation, Volume 63, Issue sup1: IIC Turin
Optional	2	2018	J.D.J. Wickens, B.J.P. Miller,	Designing a Path to an Economically, Socially and Environmentally	Studies in Conservation, Volume 63, Issue sup1: IIC Turin
Optional	2	2018	J. Sterrett, R. Piantavigna	Building an Environmentally Sustainable San Francisco Museum of	Studies in Conservation, Volume 63, Issue sup1: IIC 2018 Turin
Read	1	2017	K. Loach, J. Rowley, J.	Cultural sustainability as a strategy for the survival of museums and	International Journal of Cultural Policy, Volume 23, Issue 2:
Read	1	2015	M. Wickham, K. Lehman	Communicating sustainability priorities in the museum sector	Journal of Sustainable Tourism, Volume 23, Issue 7, pp.

Status	Priority	Year	Author(s)	Title	Publication
	1 high 2 middling 3 low				
Read	1	2015	S.S. Chitima	Developing sustainable museums through 'greening': A case study	https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvh9vwmh.12
Optional	2	2015	M.-C. Corbeil	Conservation institutions as agents of change	Studies in Conservation, Volume 60, Issue sup2: ICCROM Forum
Read	1	2012	M.S. Todorović	In search of a holistic, sustainable and replicable model for complete	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 12
Read	1	2011	K. Lithgow	Sustainable decision making—change in National Trust collections conserv	Journal of the Institute of Conservation, 34(1)
Read	1	2011	N. Blades, S. Poupard, L.	Analysing the energy consumption of conservation heating systems	
Read	1	2011	Museums, Libraries &	Capturing the outcomes of Hub museums' sustainability activities.	Journal of the Institute of Conservation, Volume 34, Issue 1
Read	1	2010	B. Hayton	Sustainability and Public Museum Buildings: The UK Legislative	Studies in Conservation: The Journal of the International Institute
Read	1	2010	Dervilla O'Dwyer	The Contribution of Conservators to Sustainability at the National	Studies in Conservation. Vol. 55, No. 3
Optional	2	2009	D. Martin	Sustainable Temporary Exhibitions	Museum Practice 45
Optional	1	2009	Museums Association	Sustainability and Museums—Report on Consultation	Museums Association, 3
Optional	1	2008	D. Martin	A Sustainable Future	Museums Journal 108.6
Optional	2	2007	T. Holmes	Eco-Visualization: Promoting Environmental Stewardship in the	The Journal of Museum Education, Vol. 21, No. 2, Place-Based
Optional	1	2007	R.J. Hebda	Museums, Climate Change and Sustainability	Museum Management and Curatorship, Volume 22, Issue 4
Optional	1	2006	D. Martin	The Green Door	Museum Practice 33
Optional	1	2006	G. Laurie	Case Study. Working Knowledge: GoingGreen	Museum Practice 33
Optional	2	2005	G.C. Sutter, D. Worts	Negotiating a sustainable path: Museums and societal therapy	Looking Reality in the Eye: Museums and Social Responsibility
Optional	1	2005	M. Cassar	Climate Change and the Historic Environment	London: University College London, Centre for Sustainable
Optional	3	2002	P.B. Hatchfield	Pollutants in the Museum Environment: Practical Strategies for	London:
Optional	3	2020		The CCI Channel Crate: Making a Lightweight, Reusable Crating	Canadian Conservation Institute (CCI) Notes 20/1
Optional	3	202	S. Michalski, J. Druzik	LED Lighting in Museums and Art Galleries	CCI Technical Bulletin 36
Optional	2	2018	Wickens, Joelle D. J., Miller,	Designing a Path to an Economically, Socially and Environmentally	Studies in Conservation, Volume 63, 2018 - Issue sup1: IIC Turin
Optional	3	2018	Chiwara, Davison	Sustainable Pest Management Through Preventive Conservation:	Studies in Conservation, Volume 63, 2018 - Issue sup1: IIC Turin
Reading	1	2018	Taylor, Joel, Boersma, Foekje	Managing Environments for Collections: The Impact of International	Studies in Conservation, Volume 63, 2018 - Issue sup1: IIC Turin
Optional	3	2017	Bell, Julianna, Newnham,	Tea: An Alternative Adsorbent for the Preservation of Cellulose	AICCM Bulletin, Volume 38, 2017 - Issue 2
Optional	2	2017	Pearlstein, Ellen	Teaching Sustainable Collection Care	Journal of the American Institute for Conservation, Volume 56,
Reading	1	2016	Atkinson, Jo Kirby	Preventive conservation and the environment: Summary of IIC Hong	Studies in Conservation, Volume 61, 2016 - Issue sup1: The
Optional	3	2015	Willet, L., Newnham, M., Nel,	'Preliminary testing of tea leaves as alternative adsorbents for	AICCM Bulletin, Volume 36, 2015 - Issue 2
Optional	3	2014	Miloš Stupar, Milica Ljaljević	A subaerial biofilms investigation and new approach in biocide	Indoor and Built Environment 2014, Vol. 23 (4), 584–593
Not accessible	1	2014	Staniforth, Sarah	Environmental conditions for the safeguarding of collections: Future	Studies in Conservation, Volume 59, 2014 - Issue 4
Optional	1	2014	Blickerstheth, Julian	Environmental conditions for safeguarding collections: What should	Studies in Conservation, Volume 59, 2014 - Issue 4
Optional	3	2013	Nigel R. Larkin	Infrared thermal imaging as a collections management tool	Journal of Natural Science Collections 2013: Volume 1
Optional	3	2010	Mark Gilberg, Charlotte Eng &	Illuminating art using a daylight system at the Broad Contemporary	WAAC Newsletter, Volume 32, Number 2, May 2010
Optional	3	2010	Dale Paul Kronknight	'Caution Urged when Considering LED Light Sources for	Conservation Dist List
Optional	3	2010	Alterio, S., Barbaro, S.,	'Microclimate Management for the Preservation of Cultural Heritage'	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 10
Optional	2	2008	Merriman, Nick	Museum collections and sustainability	Cultural Trends, Volume 17, 2008 - Issue 1
Optional	1	2007		Experts' Roundtable on Sustainable Climate Management Strategies	
Optional	3	2003	Gatenby, S., Townley, P.	'Preliminary research into the use of the essential oil of Malaleuca	AICCM Bulletin, Volume 28, 2003 - Issue 1
Optional	2	2000	Blades, Nigel, Cassar, May,	Preventive conservation strategies for sustainable urban pollution	Tradition and innovation: Contributions to the 2000 IIC Congress,
Optional	1	2020		Sustainability Management in Museums: A New Approach to	
Optional	1	2019	International Council of	'Resolutions adopted by ICOM's 34th General Assembly, Kyoto,	
Optional	1	2016	Bickerstheth, Julian	'IIC and ICOM-CC 2014 Declaration on environmental guidelines'	Studies in Conservation, 61:sup1
Optional	2	2009	Patricia Silence	'Green Task Force Survey'	(presented at the Issue Session of AIC 37th Annual Meeting, Los
Optional	1	2008	IIC and the National Gallery of	Climate Change and Museum Collections	
Optional	1	na	National Museum Directors'	Environmental sustainability - reducing museums' carbon footprint	https://www.nationalmuseums.org.uk/what-we-do/climate-crisis/en
Optional	1	2020	Sarah Sutton Brophy and	'Saving Collections and the Planet'	American Association of Museums
Optional	3	1972	United Nations Educational,	Convention Concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and	UNESCO World Heritage Centre.
Optional	1	na	ICCROM	Green Museums, a step by step guide	https://ocm.iccrom.org/documents/green-museums-step-step-guid
Optional	3	2019	P. Querner, E. Oberthaler, M.	'Biological Pest Control of a Biscuit Beetle (Stegobium Paniceum)	Studies in Conservation, Vol. 64, Issue 7
Optional	2	2018	D. Chiwara	'Sustainable Pest Management Through Preventive Conservation:	Studies in Conservation, Vol. 63, Issue sup1: IIC Turin Congress
Optional	3	1963	P. Gallo	'Problems in the use of insecticides on occupied premises'	Recent advances in conservation: contributions to the IIC Rome
Optional	3	2017	Reverberi Andrea P.,	New Trends in the Synthesis of Nanoparticles by Green Methods	Chemical engineering transactions, Vol 61
Optional	3	2020	Pei, Qiang Qiang, Wang, Xu	Action Mechanism of Sticky Rice-Paste-Modified Site Soil: A	Studies in Conservation, Volume 65, Issue 4
Optional	3	2016	Obie, Chandra	Blown Up: Collaborative Conservation and Sustainable Treatment for	Journal of the American Institute for Conservation, Volume 55,
Optional	2	2012	Lorusso, S., Braida, A.	'Art and environment as media for ecosustainability, ethics and	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 12
Optional	3	2011	Haude, Mary Elizabeth, Robin	'Plastics are forever: wraps, tools, films, and containers used in	AIC news 36, no. 5
Optional	2	2010	Müge Akkar Ercan	Creating Sustainable Communities In Historical Heritage Sites:	Conservation and the Eastern Mediterranean: Contributions to the
Optional	3	2008	Singh, M & Garg, M.	Utilization of waste lime sludge as building materials	
Optional	3	2008	Paz Sáez-Pérez, M.	The Influence of Solar Radiation on the Deterioration of the Marble	Studies in Conservation, Volume 53, 2008 - Issue 3
Optional	3	2007	Stephanie Hollner et al.	'Environmentally-Friendly Treatments for the Protection of Iron	Metals 07, Interim Meeting of the ICOM-CC Metal Working Group,
Optional	3	2000	Barry Kaye, David	'Supercritical Drying: A New Method for Conserving Waterlogged	Studies in Conservation 45 (2000)
Optional	3	1991	Caneva, G., Nugari, M.P.,	Biology in the Conservation of Works of Art	Rome: ICCROM. Miller, G.T. Jr., Spoolman, S.E. (2012) Sustaining
Optional	3	1990	Blank, Sharon	An Introduction to plastics and rubbers in collections	Studies in Conservation (1990) 35
Optional	3	1984	Winter, John	Natural adhesives in East Asian paintings	Adhesives and consolidants: Contributions to the 1984 IIC
Optional	3	1984	Masuda, Katsuhiko	Vegetable adhesives used in the workshop of the Hyogushi, restorer	Adhesives and consolidants: Contributions to the 1984 IIC
Optional	3	1981	Sease, Catherine	The case against using soluble nylon in conservation work	Studies in Conservation (1981) 26
Optional	3	2010	Beck, K., Brunetaud, X.,	'On the use of eggshell lime and tuffeau powder to formulate an	Geological Society London Special Publications 331 (1)
Optional	3	2019	Yiming, J., Sciutto, G., Prati,	'A new bio-based organogel for the removal of wax coating from	Heritage Science 7(1)
Optional	3	2019	Ranalli, G., Zanardini, E.,	'Onsite advanced biocleaning system for historical wall paintings	Journal of Applied Microbiology, 2019 June, 126(6)
Optional	3	2018	Santos, R., Melo, R. A.	'Global shortage of technical agars: back to basics (resource	Journal of Applied Phycology, 30
Optional	3	2018	Di Vito, Maura, Bellardi, Maria	'Hydrolates and Gellan: An Eco-innovative Synergy for Safe	Studies in Conservation, Volume 63, Number 1
Optional	2	2016	Misa Tamura	'A shortage of Agar'	The Magazine of the Institute of Conservation, September 2016,

Status	Priority	Year	Author(s)	Title	Publication
Optional	3	2015	Baglioni M, Jáidar Benavides	'An amine-oxide surfactant-based microemulsion for the cleaning of	J Colloid Interface Sci
Optional	3	2014	Laura Micheli, Claudia	'New Strategy for the Cleaning of Paper Artworks: A Smart	Advances in Chemistry, Volume 2014
Optional	1	2012	Martin Moeller, Krzysztof	'Volume 10: Polymers for a Sustainable Environment and Green	Polymer Science: A Comprehensive Reference
Optional	3	2008	Li, H., X. Yu, Y. Jin, W. Zhang,	'Development of an Eco-Friendly Agar Extraction Technique from the	Bioresource Technology 99, no. 8: 3301-5
Optional	3	2001	Siyam, T.	'Development of Acrylamide Polymers for the Treatment of Waste	Designed Monomers and Polymers 4, no. 2: 107-68
Optional	3	2000	Abdallah, D.J., and R.G.	'Organogels and Low Molecular Mass Organic Gelators'	Advanced Materials 12, no. 17: 1237-47
Optional	3	2014	M. Stupar, M. L.J. Grbić, A.	'Antifungal activity of selected essential oils and biocide	South African Journal of Botany 93, 118–124
Optional	3	1992	Brandis, L.	'A preliminary investigation into the effectiveness of eucalyptus oil	AICCM Bulletin, Volume 18, 1992 - Issue 1-2
Optional	3	2015	Uzoigwe, C., J.G. Burgess,	'Biomulsifiers Are Not Biosurfactants and Require Different	Front Microbiol. 6: 245
Optional	3	2007	Stevens, C.	'Silicones and Their Impact on the Environment'	Inorganic Polymers, 925
Optional	3		ECO U.S.A.	'Recycled Silicone Oil – Siloxane'	
Optional	3	2013	Norwood, W. P., M. Alaei, E.	'Decamethylcyclpentasiloxane (D5) Spiked Sediment:	Chemosphere 93, no. 5: 805-12
Optional	3	2014	ECHA Europäische	'Annex XV Restriction Report : Proposal For A Restriction :	
Optional	3	2002	Cserhádi, T., E. Forgács, and	'Biological Activity and Environmental Impact of Anionic	Environment International 28, no. 5: 337-48
Optional	3	2020	Tudor Cosmin Iurcovschi,	'New Ecological Solutions Involved in the Cleaning of a 19th Century	Applied Sciences
Optional	3	2019	Palla, F., Rotolo, V., Giordano,	'Biotechnology: a Source of Knowledge in Agreement with Green	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 19
Optional	3	2016	Palla, F.	'Blue-Biotechnology and Biocleaning of Historic-Artistic Artifacts'	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 16
Optional	3	2013	Palla, F.	'Bioactive molecules: innovative contributions of biotechnology to	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 13
Optional	2	2014	Bosch-Roig, P., Giancarlo, R.	'The safety of biocleaning technologies for cultural heritage'	Frontiers in Microbiology 5:155
Optional	2	2009	Ian Gibb et al	'Greener Cleaning of Large Textiles'	paper presented at Green: Towards Sustainability in Conservation, Green Chemistry 9
Optional	2	2007	Michaela Sousa et al.	'The Art of CO2 for Art Conservation: A Green Approach to Antique	
Optional	3	2008	Achim Unger and Helene Tello	'Handle with Care: the Dry Cleaning and Decontamination of	Preprints of the ICOM Committee for Conservation (ICOM-CC)
Optional	3		Natalie Richards	'Finding Alternatives to Petroleum-based Aromatic Hydrocarbon	(poster presented at Green)
Optional	3		Harby Ezzeldeen and	'Practical Applications of Protease Enzyme to Remove Animal Glue	(poster presented at Green)
Optional	3	2019	Ranalli, G., Zanardini, E.,	'Onsite advanced biocleaning system for historical wall paintings	Journal of Applied Microbiology, 2019 June, 126(6)
Optional	3	2018	Rampazzo, M., Manente, S.,	'How traces of pollutants in the environment modify bioremediation	Journal of Cultural Heritage, Volume 30
Optional	3	2018	Ranalli, G., Zanardini, E.,	'Hi-tech restoration by two-steps biocleaning process of Triumph of	Journal of Applied Microbiology, 2018 Sep, 125(3)
Optional	3	2016	Wolejko, E., Wydro, U.	'The ways to increase efficiency of soil bioremediation'	Ecological Chemistry and Engineering 23(1)
Optional	3	2015	Martino, M., Schiavone, S.,	'Bioremoval of Sulphate Layer from a 15th Century Polychrome	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol. 5
Optional	3	2015	an der Brand, T. P., Roest, K.,	'Potential for beneficial application of sulfate reducing bacteria in	World journal of microbiology and biotechnology, 2015 Nov 31(11)
Optional	3	2015	Balloi, A., Lombardi, E.,	'Sulfate Reducing Bacteria as Bio-cleaning Agents: Development of	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol 15, No. 2
Optional	3	2014	Dhami, N. K., Reddy, M. S.,	'Application of calcifying bacteria for remediation of stones and	Frontiers in Microbiology
Optional	3	2014	Bosch-Roig, P. & Lustrato,	'Biocleaning of Cultural Heritage stone surfaces and frescoes: which	Annals of Microbiology 65(3)
Optional	3	2013	Troiano, F., Gulotta, D., Balloi,	'Successful combination of chemical and biological treatments for	International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation, Volume 85,
Optional	3	2011	Gioventu, E., Lorenzi, P. F.	'Bio-Removal of Black Crust from Marble Surface: Comparison with	Procedia Chemistry 8
Optional	3	2010	Asociación RUVID	'Bacteria that clean art: Restorers and microbiologists use bacteria	ScienceDaily
Optional	3	2007	Polo, A., Cappitelli, F.,	'Feasibility of Removing Surface Deposits on Stone Using Biological	Microbial Ecology 60(1)
Optional	3	2006	Cappitelli F., Toniolo, L.,	'Advantages of using microbial technology over traditional chemical	Applied Environmental Microbiology, 2007 September 73 (17)
Optional	3	2006	Dhami, N. K., Reddy, M. S.,	'Improved methodology for bioremoval of black crusts on historical	Applied and Environmental Microbiology 2006 May; 72(5)
Optional	3	2006	Fernandes, P.	'Applied microbiology and biotechnology in the conservation of	Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology 73(2)
Optional	3	2005	Ranalli, G., Alfano, G., Belli,	'Biotechnology applied to cultural heritage: bioremediation of	Journal of Applied Microbiology, 2005, 98(1)
Optional	3	2005	Antonoli, P., Zapparoli, G.,	'Art-loving bugs: the resurrection of Spinello Aretino from Pisa's	Proteomics, 2005 June 5(9)
Optional	3	2003	Rodríguez Navarro, C.,	'Conservation of Ornamental Stone by Myxococcus xanthus-induced	Applied and Environmental Microbiology April 2003, 69 (4)
Optional	3	1997	Sorlini, C.	'The use of microorganisms for the removal of sulphates on artistic	International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation
Optional	3	1988	Atlas, R. M., Chowdhury, A.	'Microbial calcification of gypsum - rock and sulfated marble'	Studies in Conservation, Volume 33, 1988 - Issue 3
Optional	3	1966	Miller, J. D. A., Wakerley, D. S.	'Growth of Sulphate-reducing Bacteria by Fumarate Dismutation'	Microbiology, Volume 43, Issue 1
Optional	3	1955	Grossman, J. P., Postgate, J.	'The metabolism of malate and certain other compounds by	Journal of General Microbiology
Optional	2	2003	C. Carlon, L. Fozzati, A.	'Seaport decline and cultural heritage sustainability issues in the UK	Conservation Science in Cultural Heritage, Vol. 3
Optional	2	2003	Pinder, David, and Adalberto	'Coastal cultural heritage and sustainable development: introduction.	Journal of Cultural Heritage 1, no. 4 (2003): 3-4.
Optional	3	2021	Edited By Cornelius Holtorf,	Cultural Heritage and the Future	Routledge
Optional	3	2019	Farid Chemat, Maryline	'Green extraction of natural products. Origins, current status, and	Trends in Analytical Chemistry, Vol.118, 248-263
Optional	1	2018	Clarke CJ, Tu WC, Levers O, B	Green and sustainable solvents in chemical processes	Chem. Rev. 2018, 118, 2, 747–800
Optional	2	2019	Skanavis, Constantina,	Climate Change Communication: A Friendly for Users App	Addressing the Challenges in Communicating Climate Change
Optional	2	2019	Skanavis, Constantina,	Linaria Port: An Interactive Tool for Climate Change Awareness in	Addressing the Challenges in Communicating Climate Change
Optional	1	2019	Sutton, Sarah	Creating Change in the United States' Museum Field: Using	Addressing the Challenges in Communicating Climate Change
Optional	1	2012	Devi Kausar	Sustainability in the Management of World Cultural Heritage	Vision for Global Tourism Industry-Creating and Sustaining
Optional	2	1994	Waller, Robert	Conservation Risk Assessment: A Strategy for Managing Resources	Studies in Conservation 39, no. sup2 (1994): 12-16.
Optional	3	1994	Erhardt, David and Marion	Relative humidity re-examined	Studies in conservation, 39(sup2), pp.32-38.
Optional	1	1994	Ashley-Smith, Jonathan, Nick	Let's be honest—realistic environmental parameters for loaned	Studies in Conservation 39, no. sup2 (1994): 28-31
Optional	1	2018	Bratasz, Lukasz, Tim White,	Toward Sustainable Collections Management in the Yale Peabody	Bulletin of the Peabody Museum of Natural History 59, no. 2
Optional	2	2011	Bülow, A. E., and A. W.	The QALY in Collection Care: A Cost Effectiveness Approach to	ICOM-CC 16th Triennial Conference Lisbon Preprints, pp. 1-10.
Read	1	2023	JoAnn Cassar, Charles	Sustainability of Traditional, Historical Roofs in the Mediterranean: A	Sustainability 2023, 15(17), 12723;
Read	1	2023	Şebnem Ertuş Beşir	Determination of Conservation–Reuse Parameters for Industrial	Sustainability 2023, 15(8), 6796;
Read	1	2023	Margherita Palmieri, Bruno	The Environmental Footprint of Scientific Research: Proposals and	Sustainability 2023, 15(7), 5616;
Read	1	2017	European Environment	Glossary. List of environmental terms used by EEA	https://www.eea.europa.eu/ds_resolveuid/3WYDTH2S4A
Read	2	2021	Labadi, Sophia, Francesca	Heritage and the sustainable development goals: policy guidance for	International Journal of Heritage Studies (2021)
Read	1	2022	Oomen, A. G., L. G.	Towards Safe and Sustainable Advanced (Nano)materials. A	National Institute for Public Health and the Environment,
Read	1	2020	American Institute for	Environmental guidelines.	Conservation-wiki. American Institute for Conservation
Read	1	2001	National Information	Environmental Conditions for Exhibiting Library and Archival	An American National Standard. Vol. 79. Niso Press, 2001.
Read	1	2024	González-Parrá, Jesús	The Use of Plant Extracts as Sustainable Corrosion Inhibitors for	Sustainability 16, no. 5 (2024): 1868.
Read	1	2018	Verma, Chandrabhan, Eno E.	An overview on plant extracts as environmental sustainable and	Journal of molecular liquids 266 (2018): 577-590.

Status	Priority	Year	Author(s)	Title	Publication
Read	1	2022	Zakeri, Ali, Elnaz Bahmani,	Plant extracts as sustainable and green corrosion inhibitors for	Corrosion Communications 5 (2022): 25-38.
Read	1	2024	Zaratti, Camilla, Livia	Evaluation of Fatty Acid Methyl Esters (FAME) as a Green Alternative	Applied Sciences 14, no. 5 (2024): 1970.
Read	1	2017	Volpi, Francesca.	"Green strategies for the cleaning of works of art setting up of an	[Dissertation thesis], Alma Mater Studiorum Università di Bologna.
Read	1	2024	Luke Olbrich	Evolution of the Conservation of Cultural Heritage in a Time of	Ongoing research at the university of bologna
Optional	3	2023	Cruciotti, Massimo	Handbook of good practices for digitalisation and promotion of	
Read	1	2023	Casini, Andrea, David	"Advanced methodologies for the cleaning of works of art."	Science China Technological Sciences 66, no. 8 (2023):
Read	1	2023	Melchiorre, Chiara, Massimo	"Green solvents and restoration: Application of biomass-derived	Journal of Cultural Heritage 62 (2023): 3-12.
Read	1	2024	Bertolin, Chiara, and Filippo	"Sustainable management of heritage buildings in long-term	International Journal of Building Pathology and Adaptation
Optional	3	2013	Baglioni, Piero, David	"Colloid and materials science for the conservation of cultural	Langmuir 29, no. 17 (2013): 5110-5122.
Optional	3	2015	Baglioni, Michele, Yareli	"An amine-oxide surfactant-based microemulsion for the cleaning	Journal of colloid and interface science 440 (2015): 204-210.
Optional	3	2014	Baglioni, Piero, Debora Berti,	"Micelle, microemulsions, and gels for the conservation of cultural	Advances in colloid and interface science 205 (2014): 361-371.
Optional	3	2012	Rathousky, Jiri, Vit Kalousek,	"Nanomaterials and nanotechnologies for the conservation of the	NSTI-Nanotech 2012, www.nsti.org, ISBN 978-1-4665-6274-5 Vol. 1
Optional	1	2023	PACCIN	PACCIN Webinar: Sustainable Crating and Packing	
Optional	3	2022	Walsh-Korb, Zarah, Ingrid	"Morphological study of bio-based polymers in the consolidation of	Materials 15, no. 2 (2022): 681.
Read	1	2013	Hernandez, Christian.	"The Green Challenge': Incorporating Sustainable Practices and	PhD diss., Fashion Institute of Technology, Fashion and Textile
Optional	3	2016	Petrella, Greta, Claudia	A new sustainable and innovative work for paper artworks cleaning	International Journal of Conservation Science 7, no. SpecialIssue1
Read	1	2020	Dedeoglu, Defne	GREEN MUSEUMS: AN INTRODUCTION AND A POSSIBLE	Master's Thesis, Department of Archaeology İhsan Doğramacı
Read	1	2016	Ashley Marie Reclite	THE EVOLVING MUSEUM: GOING GREEN IN COLLECTIONS	Master's thesis, Master of Arts in Museum StudiesSan Francisco
Read	1	2001	Alan D. Curzons, David J. C.	So you think your process is green, how do you know?—Using	Green Chemistry, 2001, 3, 1–6
Optional	3	2013	Rathousky, Jiri, Monika	Micellar solutions as environmentally-friendly agents for cleaning	In NSTI-Nanotech, vol. 1, pp. 622-625. 2013.
Optional	3	2023	Ioan, Mihaela, Dan Florin	"Novel microemulsions with essential oils for environmentally	Nanomaterials 13, no. 17 : 2430.
Optional	3	2024	Paolino, Benedetta, Maria	"Greener solutions for biodeterioration of organic-media cultural	Heritage Science 12, no. 1 (2024): 1-20.
Optional	1	2023	Chris Barber, PACCIN	PACCIN Crating+Packing Sustainability Webinar	
Optional	1	2007	Camuffo, D., and V. della Vale.	"Experts' Roundtable on Sustainable Climate Management	enerife, Spain (2007).
Optional	1	2009	Carretti, Emiliano, Emiliano	"Nanoscience for Art Conservation: Oil-in-Water Microemulsions	Angewandte Chemie-German Edition 121, no. 47 (2009): 9128.
Optional	1	2020	Ricci, Chiara, Francesca	"Developing new cleaning strategies of cultural heritage stones: Are	Coatings 10, no. 5 (2020): 466.
Optional	2	2013	Domingues, Joana, Nicole	"INNOVATIVE METHOD FOR THE CLEANING OF WATERSENSITIVE	International Journal of Conservation Science (2013).
Optional	3	2019	Thanaa Ali Ali	The Use Of Eco-Friendly Materials in Restoration of Oil Paintings	2019 IMEKO TC-4 International Conference on Metrology for
Optional	3	2021	Jia, Yiming, Giorgia Sciuotto,	"Deep eutectic solvent and agar: a new green gel to remove	Journal of Cultural Heritage 51 (2021): 138-144.
Optional	2	2023	Selter, Elke, and Jok Madut	"Towards Sustainable Cultural Institutions for a New Nation:	Museum International 75, no. 1-4 (2023): 150-163.
Optional	1	2021	Passaretti, Arianna, Luana	"Biologically derived gels for the cleaning of historical and artistic	Applied Sciences 11, no. 8 (2021): 3405.
Optional	2	2024	Petrasz, Patrycja, Sami	"Green Alternatives for Archaeological Iron Stabilization."	Studies in Conservation (2024): 1-11.
Optional	2	2023	Pieralli, Irene, Antonella	"A Formulation for a New Environmentally Friendly Varnish for	Coatings 13, no. 9 (2023): 1566.
Optional	1	2022	Macchia, Andrea, Chiara	"Multi-analytical investigation of the oil painting "Il Venditore di	Sustainability 14, no. 7 (2022): 3972.
Optional	2	2021	Ilieş, Dorina Camelia, Nicolaie	"Investigations of the surface of heritage objects and green	Applied Sciences 11, no. 14 (2021): 6643.
Optional	2	2014	Pruteanu, Silvea, Petronela	Ecological cleaning systems for old icons painted in tempera."	Chemistry Journal of Moldova 9, no. 2 (2014).
Optional	2	2020	Iurcovschi, Tudor Cosmin,	"New Ecological Solutions Involved in the Cleaning of a 19th	Applied Sciences 10, no. 3 (2020): 1175.
Optional	2	2021	Lettieri, Mariateresa, Maurizio	"Eco-friendly protective coating to extend the life of art-works and	Coatings 11, no. 11 (2021): 1270.
Optional	3	2022	Di Vito, Maura, Lara Vergari,	"Anti-mold effectiveness of a green emulsion based on Citrus	Microorganisms 10, no. 2 (2022): 205.
Optional	3	2018	Zhang, Yuanyuan, Xuanhua	"Environment-friendly poly (2-ethyl-2-oxazoline) as an innovative	Nanomaterials 8, no. 9 (2018): 649.
Optional	3	2015	O'Hern, Robin, Geneva	"An Introduction to How the Manufacturing and Disposal of	AIC News (2015).
Optional	3	2018	Wright, Aaron M.	"Assessing the stability and sustainability of rock art sites: Insight	Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory 25, no. 3 (2018):
Optional	1	2016	Balliana, Eleonora, Giulia	"Assessing the value of green conservation for cultural heritage:	International journal of conservation science 7, no. 1 (2016):
Optional	2	2020	Gravagnuolo, Antonia,	"Evaluation of environmental impacts of historic buildings	Aestimum (2020): 241-272.
Optional	3		Tate-Harte	How to Calculate the Carbon Footprint of a Painting Conservation	
Optional	1	2018	Blundo, Davide Settembre,	"Improving sustainable cultural heritage restoration work through	Journal of Cultural Heritage 32 (2018): 221-231.
Optional	2	2012	Ford, Patricia Herzog, Peter	"IPI's guide to sustainable preservation practices for managing	
Optional	2			IPI's Methodology for Implementing Sustainable Energy-Saving	
Optional	1	2023	Sanchez, Sarah A., Sarah	"Life cycle assessment of anoxic treatments for cultural heritage	" Resources, Conservation and Recycling 190 (2023): 106825.
Optional	1	2018	Pranjčić, Alenka Mauko,	"Life cycle assessment of novel consolidants and a photocatalytic	Journal of Cleaner Production 181 (2018): 293-308.
Optional	1	2022	Finch, Lorraine.	Low cost / no cost tips for sustainability in cultural heritage: reduce	
Optional	1	2024	Nunberg, Sarah, Sarah A.	"Sustainability Tools in Cultural Heritage: Life Cycle Assessment	Journal of the American Institute for Conservation (2024): 1-13.
Optional	1	2014	Settembre Blundo, Davide,	"The life cycle approach as an innovative methodology for the	Journal of cultural heritage management and sustainable
Optional	1	2019	Pendergrass, Keith L., Walker	"Toward environmentally sustainable digital preservation."	The American Archivist 82, no. 1 (2019): 165-206.
Optional	1	2019	Karoglou, Maria, Stella Sofia	"Towards a preservation–sustainability nexus: Applying LCA to	Sustainability 11, no. 21 (2019): 6147.
Read	2	2023	Markivicius, Tomas, Ollsen,	"Towards sustainable conservation science in cultural heritage:	Front. Mater. 10:1274627. doi: 10.3389/fmats.2023.1274627

As mentioned above the literature was prioritized (ranked 1 to 3) by assessing titles and abstracts for relevancy to the topic.

Literature review categories

- **Aim of publication:** Main goal in a few words
- **Focus:** Which aspects of sustainability does this source focus on? Energy, climate control, toxicity to humans or environment, carbon footprint etc.
- **Which of the following topics applies to this article?**
 - It introduces new or old conservation materials and their testing
 - It addresses sustainability in conservation, restoration and preservation practices
 - It addresses sustainability in museums and cultural heritage context in general
- **Lemma:** List all terms that are used to describe green practice or materials that are presented as green or sustainable? E.g. "bio-based", "green", "nano" etc.
- **Is a definition of these lemma given?**
- **Definitions of "green" and "sustainable":** Quote any definitions related to sustainability. Also include any other related terms you may come across and we can include in a glossary, for example, what they mean when they talk about carbon footprint etc.
- **Examples of green or not green materials or practices:** Please include the reasons stated for which they are considered sustainable or not (if given)
- **REACH registration status:**
 - Are the chemicals listed in the REACH database (click here)? If no go to question 2.If yes, question 3.
 - If there is no result: click here and open substance infocard. Note REACH no result in your review, and list the datasets in blue available.
 - If there is a result: please include the information in the 'details 'eye' and write below a. Reach registration status e.g. "Full" and b. chemical safety assessment "yes" or "no". Then list c. all datasets in blue (or all if all available). More details -> see Guidelines and workflow.
- **Further research, needs, problems:** Any problems, needs or lacking that was pointed out in current practice or conservation materials.
- **Regulations, standards or policies:** Does the article mention any regulations or standards and do any of the materials mention adhere to those or not? Noting any policies that were referred to will be useful for us as they will be reviewed also within this project
- **Green transition in other industries:** Does the article refer to any transitions into sustainable practice in other industries? If yes, which ones and in what manner?
- **Type of Resource:** Conference publication, blog, etc.
- **Specialisation:** Or any information relating to the target audience
- **Author(s) background:** Anything you can find out about the authors' educational background, professional experience and current affiliation
- **Other comments:** Any other feedback relating to this source such as includes useful charts or images etc.
- **Have you checked the bibliography?** Please check the article's bibliography and add any resources to this form if they are not in here yet. Simply adding it on top of this list is enough (author title, year, publication). We will find the article and assign a priority
- **Other notes:** This is space for any useful information that you were not sure where to add within this form. We will check this column regularly and adjust the form as needed

Appendix II - Contact Detail list

Contact list: 230 entries including personal contacts, cluster members, conservation suppliers and 160 subscribers who registered via a Qualtrics sign up form for surveys (134), newsletters (87), focus groups and other initiatives (48).

Mailchimp: 148 contacts of the Qualtrics subscribers were migrated to Mailchimp if they have selected to receive newsletters. This platform now hosts 175 subscribers in total registered for newsletters (all), surveys (68) and focus groups and other initiatives (74).

Background information: providing information about role and specialisation was optional.

1. **Qualtrics subscribers:** out of the 150 newsletter, survey and/or focus group subscribers.

Specialisation:

- Paintings conservators	53
- Glass conservators	13
- Metal conservators	16
- Other:	69
o Objects	11
o Preventive conservation	10
o Paper	8
o Wood and furniture	7
o Ceramics	7
o Organic materials	6
o Photography	6
o Modern and contemporary art	5
o Archaeological	4
o Wall paintings	3
o Polychrome sculptures	2
o Stone	2
o Textiles	2
o Books	2

o Leather	1
o Sustainability	1
o Inorganic materials	1
o Science	1
o Mosaic	1
o Natural history	1
o Risk analysis	1
o Dead plants on paper	1

Job role:

- Conservator	131
- Conservation scientist	14
- Curator	1
- Other:	9
o Collection Manager	3
o Student	3
o Research Technician	2
o Digital Carpologist	1
o Conservation administrator	1
o Heritage Scientist	1
o Preventive conservator	1

2. **MailChimp subscribers:** background information such as location based on IP address not available (paid feature); explanation of “other” cannot be filled in due to limitations of the MailChimp signup form.

Job role:

- Conservator	77
- Conservation scientist	18
- Curator	3
- Other	15

Specialisation

- Paintings	40
- Glass	12
- Metals	19
- Other	74

Green(er) Conservation Tools - Survey Statistics

Date: August 2023 – August 2024 (active collection ended December 2023 i.e. most responses were collected during that time period)

Dissemination: GoGreen social media channels (and sharing by partners), GoGreen Survey subscribers, AIC Global Conservation Forum, closed conservation Facebook groups

Responses: 149 (minimum of Q1 answered in 101 surveys)

Demographic: background info was optional – see lists and charts below.

What is your specialisation? (optional)

What is your specialisation? (optional)

Book and paper conservator

paintings conservation

Restauradora, investigadora y docente.

Materials development

Conservator / Restorer

paintings

Photographic Materials Conservation

Conservation Science

book and paper conservation

Preventive conservation

textiles

objects

Objects (archaeological and historical)

Arts du Feu (céramique, verre)

Books

sculpture

Objets archéologiques

Archaeological Conservator

Restauration céramiques

Arts du feu (céramiques, verres, émaux)

Experience - For how long have you worked as a conservator? *(optional)*

72 Responses

■ > 10 years ■ 5 - 10 years ■ < 5 years ■ I am a student

Workplace - What type of work place have you worked in? *(optional)*

Multiple answers possible - Selected Choice

72 Responses

■ Library ■ Archive ■ Other ■ University ■ Museum ■ Private practice

Other - Text

13 Responses

Other - Text

regional center

laboratoire de restauration

Conservation lab

Service archéologique

Public authority

Service archéologique

Institut de Conservation

Monuments historiques

Ecole essa

INP

Federal government cultural institution

research institute

service archéologique

Country - What country or countries have you mostly worked in? (optional)

63 Responses

Definition & Parameter Feedback - Survey Statistics

Date: Ongoing.

Dissemination: GoGreen social media channels (and sharing by partners), GoGreen Survey subscribers, AIC Global Conservation Forum, closed conservation Facebook groups, GoGreen survey distribution list (mostly including various international and regional conservation institutions, universities and museums).

Responses: 215 (minimum of Q1 answered in 83 surveys).

Demographic: background info was optional – see lists and charts below.

Educator

Collection manager

Conservation professional

Experience - For how long have you worked as a conservator? (optional)

69 Responses

■ > 10 years ■ 5 - 10 years ■ < 5 years ■ I am a student

Country - What country or countries have you mostly worked in? (optional)

57 Responses

Appendix III - Tools for Greener Conservation Survey

Survey Statistics

Date: August 2023 – August 2024 (active collection ended December 2023 i.e. most responses were collected during that time period).

Dissemination: GoGreen social media channels (and sharing by partners), GoGreen Survey subscribers, AIC Global Conservation Forum, closed conservation Facebook groups.

Responses: 149 (minimum of Q1 answered in 101 surveys).

1

GoGreen - Tools for green(er) conservation

Survey results - October 2024

Progress

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Responses
Progress	0.00	100.00	61.88	149

Out of 149 responses 101 respondents provided answers.

Purpose: Knowing current use of available tools; and which type of information conservators seek or find lacking in tools; how open they are for a new tool like the GoGreen DSA

Questions list: survey branches into conservators that use tools and that do not currently use tools to judge the environmental impact of treatments.

Due to the branching of the survey into tool users and non-users the response count is not representative for completion rate as not all respondents were shown all questions.

Q1 - Which tools that provide information about the sustainability of materials or treatments do you know? *Multiple answers possible - Selected Choice*

101 Responses

The following questions were shown to respondents who know and / or use tools:

Q2a - How often do you estimate that you use tools to judge the impact of your conservation materials or treatment?

68 Responses

Comments (optional)

6 Responses

Comments (optional)

Pas assez souvent. Je suis encore dans la courbe d'apprentissage pour optimiser le temps pour leur utilisation

Using informative platforms and websites or collegial advice is not considered in my case as using a tool.

J'utilise essentiellement l'outil d'évaluation des risques de dégradation des peintures e.PRI

The main evaluation I carry out regards the safety of solvents, reagents and restoration products and guidelines for their correct disposal, but I have never completed a quotation of their impact in terms of CO2 emission or water waste or other related parameters for their production or use. I would say that I don't have tools that are easy to use for a complete evaluation of the direct and indirect impact of the products. This regards equipments as well, since I don't assess their consumptions in terms of kw/h

je ne comprends pas la question :% de temps de quoi ?

In my private lab I discover my mayor carbon foot print was on transport, the carbon footprint of materials was small so now I don't do the calculations for all the projects because many are similar and use similar quantities of materials. The energy foot print was also small

Q3a - What information about products or treatments are you retrieving from these tools? *Multiple answers possible - Selected Choice*

50 Responses

Carbon calculator (please specify) - Text

3 Responses

Carbon calculator (please specify) - Text

Stich

STICH

stich, epa

Other (please specify) - Text

1 Responses

Other (please specify) - Text

transport

Q4a - What information about products or treatments is missing or lacking in these tools? *Multiple answers possible - Selected Choice*

47 Responses

Carbon calculator (please specify) - Text

2 Responses

Carbon calculator (please specify) - Text

I only can extrapolate from other fields sources: Greenpeace...

how the product is manufactured

Q4a_Other (please specify) - Text

9 Responses

Other (please specify) - Text

Not sure, I haven't used these resources recently

je ne saurais dire

Gestion des risques pour l'objet pour l'aide à la décision. Exemple risques pour l'objet si un matériaux plus durable peut être utilisé mais considéré comme moins bon selon les critère de conservation-restauration (réversibilité, jaunissement, etc..)

NA

I cannot tell that it is missing as I've not been looking for it.

Ne sais pas

Surveillance action climatique sur la conservation

je ne sais pas

How is it produced, where and whatbare the consequences

Q5a - How would you rate the tools that you are using overall?

Please rate the tools that you are using overall? *Please rate the tool(s) on a scale from bad (0) to excellent (10).*

Average score: Accessibility (e.g. free, registration)

41 Responses

Average score: Ease of use (e.g. user friendly interface)

40 Responses

Average score: Type and quality of information

40 Responses

Q5a - Comments (optional)

4 Responses

Comments (optional)

gh

Je n'utilise pas assez ces outils pour répondre

In my opinion, the main problem related to the currently available tools is that they are hardly specific for conservators and it's hard to have an easy and complete evaluation customized to the treatment

most carbon calculators I use, are made for USA

Q6a - The information provided by the tools is...

Please indicate on the scale how strongly you disagree (0) or agree (10).

...easy to put into practice

35 Responses

...suitable for private practice

34 Responses

...suitable for museums, archives and other organisations

34 Responses

...suitable to my geographical location

34 Responses

Q6a_12 - ...too expensive to implement

31 Responses

Q6a - Comments (optional)

8 Responses

Comments (optional)

It is difficult to assess "the tools" collectively. Each tool should be assessed individually.. this does make much sense

Time required to learn how to use the tools is difficult.

Idem

Expensive to implement but benefits are proportional to the investment

pas d'avis sur la question

I work for a government institution, the difficulty of overcoming the “always choose the lowest bidder” culture can not be understated when trying to make green choices.

In my opinion, there's a lack of knowledge of useful alternatives for greener practices and products. Firstly, because there's no tool for a quantitative and qualitative evaluation of traditional practices and materials for their direct and indirect impact (for material use, production, and disposal). Therefore, it's hard to quantify a more sustainable solution. In addition, some sustainable materials are more expensive, not to mention how in Italy it's pricey to take care correctly of waste if you are a private/small conservation enterprise

Do we really need to invest? Can something be done with what we already have? Also why to charge for information ? This shouldbe given for free due to the emergency.

The following questions were shown to respondents who do not know or do not use any tools:

Q2b - Would you be interested in using such a tool in the future? *If not or if you are unsure, please explain why.* - Selected Choice

45 Responses

■ I am not sure, because...
 ■ No, because...
 ■ Yes

No, because... - Text

No data found - your filters may be too exclusive!

Q2b_16_TEXT - I am not sure, because... - Text

6 Responses

I am not sure, because... - Text

I don't know which ones are accurate

they seem to offer simple answer when maybe this isn't possible

je comprends mal l'anglais

Avant les outils numériques, il y a le bon sens, et les leçons de l'expérience

je n'utilise que des produits connus dans leur toxicité donc je ne pense pas utiliser ce genre d'outils je regarde juste les fiches de sécurité

Je suis attentive

Q3b - What information about products or treatments would you look for in such a tool? Multiple answers possible - Selected Choice

45 Responses

Carbon calculator (please specify) - Text

2 Responses

Carbon calculator (please specify) - Text

R

Makes it easier so choose the most environmentally friendly option

Other (please specify) - Text

No data found - your filters may be too exclusive!

The following questions were shown to all respondents:

Do you have any questions, suggestions or comments regarding the GoGreen-DSA (Digital Support App) that we are building? (optional)

13 Responses

Do you have any questions, suggestions or comments regarding the GoGreen-DSA (Digital Support App) that we are building? (optional)

h

Por favor, vayan a lo básico. El sentido común es el primer paso para ese "fill the gap". La reflexión. No persigan pasar de "la nada" a una "herramienta" hiper técnica" más (app.....) que esté al otro extremo de ese todo. Miren el inicio de esta encuesta... . Herramientas para científicos y gentes de ciencia. Somos restauradores. No sabemos lo básico y quieren darnos herramientas que les resultarían útiles a ustedes. Ayúdenos a pensar a nuestra altura en un determinado sentido: GREEN. no a usar una ciencia que desconocemos.

It would be beneficial if it was practical for our type of work. Information is often geared towards industry using enormous quantities which can make it difficult to judge the true impact or risk. I think this inconsistency makes it easy to under-estimate impact/risk in a boy-who-cried-wolf way. Thanks!

It would be lovely with a "checklist" function to help you through all phases of choosing, using and disposing of materials

I hope to publish the results as soon as you get to strengthen green conservation for conservators all over the world

Un outil multi-lingual serait un vrai plus !

non

organisation in professional customer research ex. conservator/restorer

Will it be open source? There will be any fee services for the users to keep it up-to-date?

I'd like to share the software I use in private practices (photo conservation). If You are interested, please get in touch with me at this email

As a senior conservator I have experienced diverse trends in conservation and I learned a lot from the technical developments of the past 15 years. However, I do make very little use of the chemicals bottles stored in my cabinet. I greatly simplified and minimalised my interventions. You could say I have become 'green'. For consolidation I mostly use natural glues in which I add a tiny clove of garlic instead of a surfactant. Methylcellulose I also one of my great friends. I do clean less than I did and with little means. I even minimalized the surface cleanings.

In fact I never had the intention to go green. It occurred naturally for different reasons. I have always been concerned about the treatments toxicity and I like to use simple methods from which I can control the parameters. However the major change has been the way I look at the works of arts I conserve. I came to understand that we, conservators, are the carriers of a contemporary visual culture that interferes with our evaluation of the condition of the works of arts.

My point is that the way to a green conservation does not only lay in the green character of our treatment methods. If we want to go green, we have to consider if we can conserve less or differently without to compromise with the quality of treatments we carry out. Can we reconsider our evaluation of degradation? Is a good conservation treatment always what we think? New research tools and research models are possibly needed to make these reassessments.

Make it free. Workshops, information, app. This is an emergency, if not for free then no one will accept! Your house is on fire the firefighters risk their lofes for free. So this fight should be the same, investerd should stop trying to make money and held accountable for what they ve been doing up until now to the planet.

Do promote widely - e.g. for practising artists and media.

What is your specialisation? (optional)

What is your specialisation? (optional)

Book and paper conservator

paintings conservation

Restauradora, investigadora y docente.

Materials development

Conservator / Restorer

paintings

Photographic Materials Conservation

Conservation Science

book and paper conservation

Preventive conservation

textiles

objects

Objects (archaeological and historical)

Arts du Feu (céramique, verre)

Books

sculpture

Objets archéologiques

Archaeological Conservator

Restauration céramiques

Arts du feu (céramiques, verres, émaux)

Experience - For how long have you worked as a conservator? *(optional)*

72 Responses

■ > 10 years ■ 5 - 10 years ■ < 5 years ■ I am a student

Workplace - What type of work place have you worked in? *(optional)*

Multiple answers possible - Selected Choice

72 Responses

■ Library ■ Archive ■ Other ■ University ■ Museum ■ Private practice

Other - Text

13 Responses

Other - Text

regional center

laboratoire de restauration

Conservation lab

Service archéologique

Public authority

Service archéologique

Institut de Conservation

Monuments historiques

Ecole essa

INP

Federal government cultural institution

research institute

service archéologique

Country - What country or countries have you mostly worked in? (optional)

63 Responses

Appendix IV - Definition and Parameters Feedback Survey

1

Green Definition and Parameters Feedback Survey

Provisional Results - 11.02.2025

Progress

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Responses
Progress	0.00	100.00	43.78	215

Out of 215 responses 83 respondents provided answers.

Survey structure: the survey was constructed with three compulsory questions to evaluate agreement, clarity and relevance of definition and parameters on a sliding scale from 1 (not at all) to 5 (completely). Comments for each were optional in case of positive scores 4 and 5 and compulsory for the neutral and negative scores 1 to 3. It was also optional to leave additional comments and/ or background info (type of workplace, experience in years and country of work) at the end of the survey.

Summary score for all 3 questions: agreement, clarity and relevancy

83 Responses

Q1 "In general, I agree with the text."

Choose on a scale from 1 (not at all) to 5 (completely).

83 Responses

Q1 Reasons or comments (required if scored < 4)

11 Responses

Please tell us why and what specific section of the definition you are referring to.

a

My only disagreement is about the fundamental departure point, the definition of the environment. Your approach departs from the traditional narrative that the environment is exclusively a "natural environment" and the "cultural environment" is something "else." Definitions are conventional, and many approaches to defining the environment may exist. I do not mean that my definition is correct or yours is wrong; all definitions are based on conventions - what we agree upon.

I think such a divisive environment's definition of nature vs. culture unjustly disregards culture, placing it nearly on the level of a "hazard" that consumes "nature," so there is a "need" to protect nature" from culture. In extreme forms, this doctrine has led to barbarian eco-activism attacking museums and cultural heritage in the name of "environment." For example, eco-activists wouldn't go to a bird sanctuary to shoot birds with "stop oil" slogans. Still, they feel perfectly comfortable doing it in museums, as the green activism doctrine has an engrained antagonistic separation between nature and culture, which is destructive to cultural heritage, which is a part of the human environment.

My perspective, which we discussed earlier, aims for a holistic and inclusive approach in line with the policy documents of ICOMOS and current trends in green but inclusive transformation, where the cultural environment and natural environment are two sides of the same environment, and their needs must be equally protected and balanced, as both are parts of the environment are essential for sustainable living. While this is just a concept, words, language, and ideas are critical as they become policy instruments and nearly always become actions (or lack thereof).

I found the structure rather difficult to read. would it be possible to shorten?

General remark: please be more straightforward. These definitions are convoluted and verge on impractical. If the reader doesn't get your point after reading it once, they won't use it.

Holistic definition of conservation: too many buzz words, the first sentence reads like the opening of an advert for a self-help scam. Please specify what you mean by "uniquely positive", "powerful". Why should conservation support economic and societal stability? Shouldn't green conservation take an anticapitalist approach and support economic degrowth rather than "stability"? And how does social stability relate to social sustainability?

Green conservation : The articulation between conservation and green conservation is not clear.

Green parameters : the concept is very interesting, and probably the most useful aspect of this work so far. But it needs a proper introduction to what a green parameter is, how it's supposed to be used, and by whom. And the way it is written is very confusing to read, the general grammar of this section should be corrected. For example: "Hazard impacts on human and environment" is not a correct english sentence (singular nouns always require an adjective), and based on the following text could be corrected to "Hazard impacts on human health and the environment". As well, the articulation between the bullet points and the following text is not clear. For instance, many sentences start with a participle ("-ed" or "-ing") and need a proper adjective, a verb to link them to the previous bullet points, or to be rewritten.

It reads like a manifesto and is too 'fashionable' in its semantics. It contains too many relative and subjective words/ terms which are all relative to each and every conservation decision making parameter. Harmful is a statement that always is relative and risk assessments are relevant to this evaluation. I advocate for the laws of thermodynamics as essential definition in combination with the Buddhist concept 'of do no harm'.

How "green" is defined is unrealistic, it means no impact at all. I understand it's put as an ideal case, but I think it's hard to put in practice. I think most people will use "green" and "greener" interchangeably. Therefore I think it's more useful to define "green" as optimized to have an as low as an impact as possible.

I don't agree with referring to circular as an objective as such. I think it's a means to reach the objective to be environmentally friendly.

Regarding the parameters, it's not clear for me whether energy use refers to the quantity of energy consumed, or whether also the source of energy is considered (e.g. fossil vs. renewable).

In G7 it's not clear how availability and biodiversity are related. Every product can affect biodiversity if you look at the life cycle, do you refer here only to the impact of bio-based materials used in conservation?

Especially the beginning with adjectives such as "uniquely positive" and "powerful" the definition sounds more like a manifesto. This is not a problem in terms of content, but it is a bit out of the blue when you go into it thinking you are reading a "definition" as one would in a dictionary.

With regards the parameters if longevity is taken into account why not the degree of contribution to sustainability? Deaccession is an important part of conservation in the sense that resources should be prioritized for objects that truly matter. The definition does not seem to explicitly touch upon this. I understand it is a controversial topic but it is also highly important.

Also, are animal rights considered as part of the parameters, where it does not immediately relate to biodiversity or aquatic life?

The green parameters are very theoretical and seem to have little practical relevance - as an example I would like to mention the water use (in relation to what?) in the production of materials (G6).

Neither the text on conservation nor of green conservation say what they are. At the most, the text says a little, but just a little about what they "do". Mostly they turn circles around the question of what they are with no answer. If the text says anything concrete, especially with green conservation, the text says what they are not. If you can't give a definition in one or at most, two sentences, you don't have one.

The condition of Artwork or the object to be conserved dictates the action and materials required for treatment. The major responsibility of a conservator is to provide the best possible care for the heritage object. These major issue as well as the major purpose of heritage conservation - care for the heritage object - have been completely omitted in the entire statement.

Strongly agree: Cultural Heritage is endangered because of climate change and environmental destruction. Disagree that green conservators as currently defined offer significant behaviours to support those facing the consequences of extractive industries; the imaginarium envisaged in the holistic definition seems peculiarly insula and relatively achievable with little effort (and should be already written into practice) - larger dependencies seem left outwith of these definitions (eg. infrastructures both technical and social)...

Q1 Reasons or comments (optional if scored > 3)

19 Responses

Reasons or comments (optional)

I don't think that the concepts of conservation of cultural heritage and sustainability are linked in the mind of the general population. Maybe not even for the restorers themselves. Of course they should.

The concepts of the product life cycle are covered in the sub-chapters but not in a general way.

No influence in the energy level of indoor climate control

To agree completely I have to learn more about the topic. But as is, yes, I agree with it

I like this, definition, especially the 14 Green Parameters, I think the parameters are a start at trying to visualize or put into words the complexity of the issue and the various topics greening touches on. I am glad this definition did not attempt to define greening in a single paragraph, but used the 14 parameters to remind people that these issues are all interconnected in a system.

My reservations are mainly about language and structure - not about the content itself. Further editing could improve formulation and clarity. Colon (:) is used instead of semicolon (;) in one instance (G3), making reader wander for a while... (unless I missed something). As I understand them, the last few categories (G13 and G14) are not actual Green parameters but rather efficiency factors to be counterbalanced (I assume) with the Green requirements.

The definition of green parameters seem to provide the ideal absolutes. I'm curious about the scale in-between as we as a profession 'work towards' being carbon neutral, zero waste etc, acknowledge where In cases the research is developing/being problem solved, a pros cons analysis of materials and approaches etc

The word "measurable" is missing to link the definition to the parameters.

Generally, I enjoyed reading the definition and agreed with the statement, however, I had some issues with the parameters section.

For S12, I think you're trying to put too many thoughts into one statement. I think it points could be separated into several statements. I'm also not clear on the benefit of a material being a commercial product or not. Most things are purchased for use, but if something is bespoke made, is that a pro or con to greener conservation?

S14 - While I agree that ease of use and reduced time are benefits to conservators, are they "greener"? Does it make sense to include these parameters? I suppose using less time for a treatment would mean using less energy resources (lights, hvac systems, etc.). Maybe ease of use should be evaluated?

Reducing waste is particularly important given all of the supplies we use.

I agree with all of it! I only miss digital data storage under the green parameters and also specific mention of impact and energy use of the manufacturing of analytical equipment.

The amount of data we produce with the increasing use of analytical techniques/research is growing so fast. We should take this into consideration during decision making processes. Questions like: is this research and accumulated data and energy used etc. really necessary in comparison to the impact it has on the environment, should be addressed before each use.

G1 and can be easily combined.

G4 Not an issue at all in my opinion.

G11 I am missing the point here. It suggests that we can asses this, but I do not think this is entirely true.

The holistic definition is very firm, almost inflexible seeming, and doesn't seem to hold space for differing capacities, privileges held, and access to support.

Cultural heritage is endangered by not just only climate change and environmental destruction, not sure the best way to incorporate the various modes of impact on cultural heritage, but I think it would be helpful to mention some others here.

I do appreciate the statement "green conservation is an ideal we strive for", recognizing this is a process and, hopefully, one which becomes easier over time.

Very good, thorough definition of the ideal to strive for. My only hesitation is how difficult it would be to fully achieve all the time. However, using this definition to get as close as possible to the ideal is the best possible choice.

It needs some tweaks to wording. The holistic definition implies that the main reason the conservation profession should be concerned about climate change is its impact on cultural heritage. I think the definition should first speak to the profession's contribution to climate change and then note that climate change harms cultural heritage, and therefore that reducing climate change is a preservation strategy. G4 and G5 should not be confined to treatment since preventive conservation approaches and products are equally if not more impactful given the quantities used (think Ethafoam vs EcoFoam, choice of box suppliers, etc.) "Artwork specific" is too narrow. Just say "treatment"? G9 and G10 seem redundant after G4 and G5. G11, S12, S13 and S14 apply to preventive work as well. I don't think you need treatment-specific statements. For example, considering the quality of the result applies to all conservation work including preventive, documentation (imaging) and analysis.

The only aspect I miss is the starting point: what do we preserve, for whom and for how long? Not every collection item is kept for the same purpose. We as conservators need to understand that not everything can or should be conserved. One can also decide to do nothing or accept loss.

It is my understanding that only the toxicity of materials is taken into account when considering if a treatment was harmful for the conservator. I believe ergonomics, working hours, eyes strain and so forth should be considered as well

It's very well written and comprehensive

Q2 "In general, the text is clear and easy to understand."

Choose on a scale from 1 (not at all) to 5 (completely).

77 Responses

Q2 Reasons or comments (required if scored < 4)

21 Responses

Please tell us why and what specific section of the definition you are referring to.

some long sentences (in the definitions of Green Conservation and Green Parameters)

see previous answer

General remark: please be more straightforward. These definitions are convoluted and verge on impractical. If the reader doesn't get your point after reading it once, they won't use it.

Holistic definition of conservation: too many buzz words, the first sentence reads like the opening of an advert for a self-help scam. Please specify what you mean by "uniquely positive", "powerful". Why should conservation support economic and societal stability? Shouldn't green conservation take an anticapitalist approach and support economic degrowth rather than "stability"? And how does social stability relate to social sustainability?

Green conservation : The articulation between conservation and green conservation is not clear.

Green parameters : the concept is very interesting, and probably the most useful aspect of this work so far. But it needs a proper introduction to what a green parameter is, how it's supposed to be used, and by whom. And the way it is written is very confusing to read, the general grammar of this section should be corrected. For example: "Hazard impacts on human and environment" is not a correct english sentence (singular nouns always require an adjective), and based on the following text could be corrected to "Hazard impacts on human health and the environment". As well, the articulation between the bullet points and the following text is not clear. For instance, many sentences start with a participle ("-ed" or "-ing") and need a proper adjective, a verb to link them to the previous bullet points, or to be rewritten.

My reservations are mainly about language and structure - not about the content itself. Further editing could improve formulation and clarity. Colon (:) is used instead of semicolon (;) in one instance (G3), making reader wander for a while... (unless I missed something). As I understand them, the last few categories (G13 and G14) are not actual Green parameters but rather efficiency factors to be counterbalanced (I assume) with the Green requirements.

Yes, but it does not read like a definition rather than a manifesto.

Green parameters

I find it a lot of text to plow through. Maybe it's helpful to restructure with some bullet points, so you can also glance over it to get the key message. Or put it in a flow diagram for example.

I find the explanations of the parameters also hard to read, because of the use of .../....

Perhaps it is a bit long, and the emphasis on greener conservation could come out more clearly

I had to read the holistic definition a few times, then I could understand it. It is well written, but maybe not the most easily understandable language.

I do not understand some impact definitions. The definitions are mostly 1 - to me very long - sentence. This makes it harder for me to follow.

And for example G3: existing controls in place and considering the outdoor location: also considering any change in the climate control needs of the object as a result of approach/treatment under contemplation.

I do not understand what is exactly meant.

The explanations of green conservation are certainly correct, but rather difficult to understand. The list of what green conservation could mean is accompanied by a moral impetus: "Greener conservation reinforces and furthers the positive role of conservation in the sustainability of our culture."

And that is incomprehensible to me.

As a definition, the text on conservation and green conservation say nothing. They only give a vague picture of what they think they do or not.

The entire statement is too complicated and too specific.

Further explanation of terms and statements would be helpful: assessing and adapting WHICH and WHOSE professional practices; It aligns with the circular economy, is carbon neutral, zero-waste, accessible, and available: terms aren't defined, assuming readers are familiar with all these terms equally.

It's a little long.

People who are on the fence about adopting less impactful habits in their work lives are not going to be persuaded by such long, nuanced definitions and instructions about how to improve.

Too long: simplify the message. I appreciate you're trying for thorough but my attention span wandered off several times as I read the paragraph. Short, snappy, memorable is the way.

Sometimes it reads too much like a litany of wishes and the word 'green' repeated mantra-like for it to come to be

Generally a bit wordy. If it can be condensed and retain clarity, that would be preferred.

Not clear on what the difference is between green conservation and greener conservation or why 2 different terms are necessary

Apparent redundancy is confusing, as are treatment-focused statements that apply equally to other aspects of conservation work.

Q2 Reasons or comments (optional if scored > 3)

4 Responses

Reasons or comments (optional)

I realised that the text is not fully homogenous for the green parameters: "based on..." differs from "the energy/water use..." or "assessment regarding...". This could be corrected for better readability and intrinsic definition of what is a parameter.

Generally, I found the text easy to understand, but I had issues with some of the parameters, especially G9 and the last section "Art work specific / professional parameters." I think this last section would benefit from an overall edit to clarify the point/goal of the assessment criteria (what is the best option for being "Greener").

It wasn't clear to me why the number listings switched from G to S.

For G9, I believe it should be "effects" instead of "affects"; it should also be clearer what you mean. I think that you're missing the contrasting aspect of the point, likely for brevity, but it reads confusingly.

For S12, I think you're trying to put too many thoughts into one statement. I think it points could be separated into several statements.

The text is well broken down, so it reads clearly.

Re-using should come before recycling

Q3 "In general, the text is relevant to my work." Choose on a scale from 1 (not at all) to 5 (completely).

75 Responses

Reasons or comments (required if scored < 4)

13 Responses

Please tell us why and what specific section of the definition you are referring to.

In my company I am not the one who chooses the products to buy and the procedures to use. I like to be aware and avoid waste, but I have actually little decision space and positive impact. Also, the text is agreeable but vague.

I only say moderately right now, because I am waiting for wide scale adaptation. However I do think that it is in line with say, how federal governments or the SDGs define greening and will be easily accepted.

Well to some extent, but I would not find it helpful to any decision making processes to be greener.

I completely agree with the green parameters, but it is also slightly frustrating. As a museum conservator in a very hierarchical organisation, I have very little mandate in decision making.....

We use hardly any chemicals in paper conservation. I don't believe finding alternatives will have a significant impact.

The implementation of the parameters would be interesting for my work. However, as already mentioned, these are sometimes not feasible - whether due to a lack of time or simply because there are no serious sources or because there is simply no budget for an extension to the air conditioning system, for example, or for other technical requirements.

living and working in a country where conservation related materials and tools are not readily available, there is difficulty to confirm to these ideals on a daily basis.

In general, the theme is important. Specifically, it does not help.

I do not work with collection materials

There is nothing about the communities of users and practitioners who conservators ally and support against cultural destruction whether anthropogenic or otherwise; the danger of this is the definition cannot in its present form be scaled into something more meaningful beyond the profession (which the argument here assumes it needs to)

I don't have much power to make changes to how things are done institutionally. I advocate for less harmful ways of doing things but institutional regulations (particularly about things like disposal of waste, re-use or re-purposing is generally not allowed) and desire for short-term financial savings means nothing changes. This information would only be relevant to me if I could actually do something with it. Hopefully people who actually make decisions about these things will eventually decide to make some changes

95% of my work is preventive conservation. If I ignore the word "treatment", the text is very relevant. Please consider that even outside of climate control specifications (which I am delighted to see in first place as the most significant way the conservation profession contributes to climate change), preventive conservation decisions regarding the choice of approaches and products have a proportionately larger impact because they tend to be applied collection-wide or to groups of objects within collections rather than to individual objects. Think about storage methods, display case design, rehousing projects, etc. While it is true that some treatments (e.g., room-sized vats of solvent or PEG for ship-sized objects, CO2 blasting of dozens of outdoor sculptures, poulticing of large expanses of wall finish) use large quantities of products, most treatments, even when added up, have a *relatively* small carbon footprint when compared to the average preventive project. I don't think you need to point this out; this is to explain why taking the treatment references out of the definitions makes sense.

I work in conservation research, so the sections on conservation practice are less relevant to me.

Reasons or comments (optional if scored > 3)

11 Responses

Reasons or comments (optional)

In my opinion, there is one aspect missing (which was touched on in the last point on treatment quality): how do you choose between a green treatment that is often more expensive and sometimes less effective and a more traditional treatment whose effectiveness (quality of performance and duration) has already been proven, which is often less expensive but sometimes much less green?

my PhD research is on sustainability in conservation practice by developing new materials and methodology for treating artworks

Until we have more information to weigh various treatment options, we will continue to use the materials/products that will give us the best result, with the longevity we desire.

Preservation Departments don't always have control over HVAC unfortunately

As sustainability specialist it is relevant to learn how "green" is interpreted in specific domains.

We are at the moment working on greener products and testing them on case studies

It is relevant to any practicing conservator of culture heritage and this is why it has to be formulated with culture heritage in mind - with culture heritage conservation in its centre not as the marginal aspect of climate change issues.

My advocacy and efforts only go so far up the ladder, within a larger corporation.

I completely agree with the definition and strive to bring more awareness of this into my practice and to make colleagues also think about it

this is so important!

Q4 Do you have any other feedback or comments? (optional)

15 Responses

Do you have any other feedback or comments? (optional)

The definitions here presented are good starting point for raising awareness. I particularly appreciated the green parameters specifically referred to the conservation field.

it's hard to see, that some of the Parameters could be easily applied into the daily work (e.g. G5 to G8)

Congratulations on a great result. Besides noting your great results, I do not have any objections to outputs and methodology. My only disagreement is about the fundamental departure point, the definition of the environment. Your approach departs from the traditional narrative that the environment is exclusively a "natural environment" and the "cultural environment" is something "else." Definitions are conventional, and many approaches to defining the environment may exist. I do not mean that my definition is correct or yours is wrong; all definitions are based on conventions - what we agree upon.

I think such a divisive environment's definition of nature vs. culture unjustly disregards culture, placing it nearly on the level of a "hazard" that consumes "nature," so there is a "need" to protect nature" from culture. In extreme forms, this doctrine has led to barbarian eco-activism attacking museums and cultural heritage in the name of "environment." For example, eco-activists wouldn't go to a bird sanctuary to shoot birds with "stop oil" slogans. Still, they feel perfectly comfortable doing it in museums, as the green activism doctrine has an engrained antagonistic separation between nature and culture, which is destructive to cultural heritage, which is a part of the human environment.

My perspective, which we discussed earlier, aims for a holistic and inclusive approach in line with the policy documents of ICOMOS and current trends in green but inclusive transformation, where the cultural environment and natural environment are two sides of the same environment, and their needs must be equally protected and balanced, as both are parts of the environment are essential for sustainable living. While this is just a concept, words, language, and ideas are critical as they become policy instruments and nearly always become actions (or lack thereof).

You did excellent work based on the paradigm, based on one of the possible definitions of the environment. There may be other definitions of the environment, which may lead to different policy recommendations and approaches. However, having different views is not a problem; in fact, any disagreement is an excellent driver to move forward.

I recommend the fundamental laws of thermodynamics as a really good guide to making greener decisions in conservation, as they address conservation of energy, entropy and absolute zero. All concepts conservators encounter across the spectra they navigate along. Also daoism has philosophically very useful concepts and insights that are much more suited to dynamics such as sustainable development than the Western material fetishism.

I found the text very clear and well-explained. I also agree on the importance of defining what 'green' and 'sustainable' mean in our field in order to understand what we are currently doing and the goals we need to achieve.

It would be important that we publish at may be opting for what particle physicists do: adding as coauthors ALL members of the project except if they refuse. We can have a text signed by 100 scientists.

I think it's important to not look at recycling as a cure-all. Reducing waste and re-using scraps are the best options for going green.

It is very good work overall

I think it is of great interest that the products and methods could be tested on real case studies and disseminated in every country through local initiative and symposia.

Other goal could be the products AVAILABILITY to conservation products suppliers, in order to give the conservatore and restorers the opportunity to make an effective change in their everyday practice

Already given prior

There is no mention of 'commercial products' in relation to the choice of a 'green company'.

as above

Excellent work!

I agree wholeheartedly with the definitions in this document, but have some doubts about the applicability of these definitions in decision making. Yes, these matters should become part of all conservation decisions (because they should become part of essentially ALL our decision making), but I wonder how much weight 'greenness' will have or should have in conservation decisions. Can GoGreen also investigate or advise on how to balance, say, the toxicity of a solvent against the longevity of a treatment?

great work!

Specialisation - What is your professional role? (optional)

73 Responses

Other (please specify) Conservation scientist Conservator

15 Responses

Other (please specify) - Text

PhD candidate in Conservation - Restoration

PhD researcher in Heritage Science

technician

Ingegnere elettronico per controlli e diagnostica

Conservation Technician

LCA specialist

and Research Technician

Technician

Head of Conservation

Retired

Educator

faculty

Educator

Collection manager

Conservation professional

Experience - For how long have you worked as a conservator? (optional)

69 Responses

■ > 10 years ■ 5 - 10 years ■ < 5 years ■ I am a student

Country - What country or countries have you mostly worked in? (optional)

57 Responses

Appendix V - GoGreen_definition and parameters_29_08_24

Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices

Work in progress definition / 29.08.2024

Holistic Definition for Cultural Heritage Conservation

Conservation has a uniquely positive and powerful role to play in shaping a sustainable future: it preserves cultural heritage for current and future generations and increases economic and societal resilience. Cultural Heritage is endangered because of climate change and environmental destruction. Assessing and adapting professional practices to help combat these ultimate 'agents of deterioration' is therefore, in itself, cultural heritage conservation. A green conservation approach prioritises the environment and human health through holistic, heritage conservation decision-making. Aligned with conservation ethics and values it allows for future developments in the conservation field, and considers the entirety of consequences before, during and after interventions. Cultural heritage professionals should actively advocate adopting a green conservation approach, with support in accordance with the economic, social and environmental pillars of sustainability.

Green Conservation

'Green conservation' is not harmful to the environment or to the conservator. It aligns with the circular economy, is carbon neutral, zero-waste, accessible, and available. Green conservation is an ideal which we strive for through greener conservation, which takes all these aspects into consideration in line with professional guidelines, and current and continuing research. **Greener conservation** practices encompass the decisions made within the context of collection management, any preventive measure or treatment, the materials used, the frequency of treatment and long-term impacts. Greener conservation reinforces and furthers the positive role of conservation in the sustainability of our culture.

Green Parameters key factors for green conservation (further explained on page 2)

Hazard impacts on human and environment	G1	Toxicity and hazard metrics for environment
	G2	Toxicity and hazard metrics for human user
Impacts on climate change	G3	Energy – Climate control impacts
	G4	Energy – Consumption in approach/application for treatment
	G5	Energy – Conservation/treatment-associated materials/products to be used
Impacts on resources	G6	Availability – water use & resource depletion
	G7	Availability - biodiversity impacts
	G8	Waste
Art work specific/ professional parameters	G9	Material/product selection and application method
	G10	Number of applications/quantities
	G11	Longevity of result
	S12	Accessibility – availability of used materials/products and transport
	S13	Quality of result
	S14	Accessibility – Ease of use and time

The associated parameters for defining green conservation, considering conservation's strategic impact areas within the sustainable development goals

'Green conservation' is informed by the larger context of sustainability and defined by the parameters considered most relevant to conservation. This definition aims to outline environmental impacts alongside professional responsibilities and requirements within conservation decisions and practice, hereby considering the pertinent socio-economic aspects. The parameters are linked with the strategic impact areas as illustrated in the adjacent figure. This definition focuses solely on conservation. The broader environmental impacts, social aspects and implicit value of cultural heritage itself are not directly included herein.

Figure. Strategic impact areas identified within the United Nations* 17 Sustainable Development Goals. Model diagram based upon the approach from the World Green Building Council.

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Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices

Work in progress definition / 29.08.2024

Description of Principles behind Green Parameters

- G1 Toxicity and hazard metrics for environment**
Based on information and data relating to the toxicity and chemical hazards/risks of a particular material/product for the environment when used within the specific approach/treatment, as well as the toxicity and hazards for the environment considering the entire life cycle of the material/product.
- G2 Toxicity and hazard metrics for human user**
Based on information and data relating to the toxicity and chemical hazards/risks of a particular material/product for the human user within the specific approach/treatment, as well as the toxicity and hazards for humans when considering the entire life cycle of the material/product.
- G3 Energy – Climate control impacts**
The energy use related to indoor climate control for the object/collection, considering general guidelines, existing controls in place and considering the outdoor location: also considering any change in the climate control needs of the object as a result of approach/treatment under contemplation.
- G4 Energy – Consumption in approach/application for treatment**
The energy use from direct consumptions related to the considered approach/application for treating the specific object: such as any analyses needed/carried out before and during treatment, and any electrical tools used during active conservation.
- G5 Energy – Conservation/treatment-associated materials/products to be used**
The energy use associated with the manufacture of the materials/products being used in the treatment.
- G6 Availability – water use & resource depletion**
Water use in creating the material/product and water requirements for the material/product and treatment approach during use, and whether pre-processed water or tap water is required. The consideration of other resources depleted because of the treatment approach and materials/products being used.
- G7 Availability - biodiversity impacts**
An assessment of the impact on biodiversity from the materials/products used through their creation/manufacture.
- G8 Waste**
Considering the required disposal of the materials/products being used and whether they can rather be recycled, or even re-used.
- G9 Material/product selection and application method**
An assessment of the material/product and its application method within a treatment for any change in potential affects and/or impacts due to the specific combinations (e.g. solvent applied with either cotton swab, gel or tissue).
- G10 Number of applications/quantities**
The quantity of material/product used in a single application and the number of applications required to achieve the desired result within the specific treatment.
- G11 Longevity of result**
An assessment of how long the object can be in retreat as a result of the approach/treatment, and the durability and lifetime of the materials/products added to the object within the approach/treatment.
- S12 Accessibility – availability of used materials/products and transport**
The cost of the materials used in the approach/treatment (qualitatively assessed by user), and whether it is available as a commercial product for the user. Transparency of material/product information. Whether it is already present (in the studio/lab/etc) or needs to be purchased, and the consideration of transport implications accordingly.
- S13 Quality of result**
Assessment by the user of the treatment result achieved with the material/product, treatment/approach.
- S14 Accessibility – Ease of use and time**
Assessment regarding the ease of using the treatment/approach, materials/products, considering the working properties and the time needed for testing the approach, materials/product, and the time needed for carrying out the treatment approach.

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Appendix VI - GoGreen_definition and parameters_31_01_25

Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices

Work in progress definition / 31.01.25

Holistic Definition for Cultural Heritage Conservation

Conservation has a uniquely positive and powerful role to play in shaping a sustainable future: it preserves cultural heritage for current and future generations and supports economic and societal stability. Climate change and its destructive impacts endangers cultural heritage. So a vital part of cultural heritage conservation is assessing and adapting professional practices to help combat these foremost agents of change. Embedded within this sustainability context green conservation prioritizes the environment, and human health and wellbeing, through holistic decision-making. Aligned with conservation ethics and values it allows for future developments and considers the entirety of consequences within investigative, interventive and preventive practice. It involves a considered balancing of the impacts, before, during and after any decision or approach. Cultural heritage professionals should actively adopt a green conservation approach, with institutional support in accordance with the Economic, Social and Environmental pillars of sustainability.

Green Conservation

Green conservation is an aspirational, consultative process and always comparative in practice. A green conservation approach is minimally harmful to the environment and humans. Aligning with the circular economy, green conservation is decarbonizing, zero-waste, accessible, and available. We strive for green conservation through decision-making and evolving practice, which takes all these aspects into consideration in balance with professional guidelines, and current and continuing research. Green conservation practices encompass the decisions made within the context of collection management and storage, any investigative, preventive or interventive measure, their documentation, the materials used, the frequency of treatment and long-term impacts. Green conservation reinforces and furthers the positive role of conservation in the sustainability of our culture.

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Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices

Work in progress definition / 31.01.25

Green Parameters descriptors for green conservation (further explanations below)

Hazard impacts on human and environment	G1	Toxicity and hazard metrics for the natural environment
	G2	Toxicity and hazard metrics for humans
Impacts on climate change	G3	Energy – Indoor climate control impacts
	G4	Energy – Consumption in approach/application
	G5	Energy – Conservation approach/treatment-associated materials/products to be used
Impacts on resources	G6	Availability – water & resource use
	G7	Availability – biodiversity impacts
	G8	Waste
Art work specific/professional parameters	G9	Material/product selection and application method
	G10	Efficiency - Number of applications/consumption/quantities of materials/products used
	G11	Longevity of result
	G12	Accessibility – availability of approach/used materials/products
	G13	Accessibility – Ease of use and time
	G14	Quality/value impacts of result in meeting preservation goals

Description of the Green Parameters

Hazard impacts on human and environment

G1 Toxicity and hazard metrics for the natural environment

Considers the information and data relating to the toxicity and chemical hazards/risks of a particular material/product for the natural/living environment when used within the specific process/approach/treatment, as well as the toxicity and hazards for the natural/living environment considering the entire life cycle of the material/product.

G2 Toxicity and hazard metrics for humans

Considers the information and data relating to the toxicity and chemical hazards/risks of a particular material/product for the human user within the specific process/approach/ treatment, as well as the toxicity and hazards for humans when considering the entire life cycle of the material/product.

Impacts on climate change

G3 Energy – indoor climate control impacts

Considers the energy use related to indoor climate control for the object/collection, considering general guidelines, existing controls in place and the prevailing outdoor location: also considering any change in the climate control needs of the object as a result of the approach/treatment under contemplation. Considers the energy sources being used (carbon-based, non-renewable, renewable).

G4 Energy – consumption in approach/application

Considers the energy use from consumptions directly related to the approach/application being considered (i.e. during the specific implementation process). This could include any analyses needed/carried out before and during treatment, any electrical tools used during active conservation, any transformations required by end-users at extremely low or high T°C (ambient, <5°C, <100°C, >500°C, >1000°C), any specifically related energy requirements for the premises (e.g. air extraction), specifically associated transportation for artwork/materials/human, documentation and digital storage. Considers digital sobriety and the energy sources being used (carbon-based, non-renewable, renewable).

G5 Energy – conservation approach/treatment-associated materials/products to be used

Considers the energy use associated with the manufacture, supply and disposal of the materials/products being used in the approach/application. Compares the carbon footprint/GWP of the manufacture of individual products if known (e.g. STICH). Where there is an assembly of several products, each one is identified and considered as far as possible.

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Impacts on resources

G6 Availability – water & resource use

Considers the quantity of water used in creating the material/product and water requirements for the material/product and treatment/approach during use and disposal (e.g. for dilution). Considers whether pre-processed water or tap water is required (city, reclaimed, demineralized, ultra-pure). Considers other natural resources depleted because of the treatment/approach and materials/products being used (e.g. components in lighting/systems that rely on scarce mineral or ore sources). Considers the location of source extraction (local, national, regional, beyond). Considers social labor practices of the vendors and product manufacturers and considers human resource requirements for the approach.

G7 Availability - biodiversity impacts

Considers the direct impact on biodiversity from the materials/products used through their creation/manufacture.

G8 Waste

Considers the required disposal of the materials/products being used and a zero-waste hierarchy - whether they can be recycled, are biodegradable, can be repurposed or can be directly reused, whereby waster is avoided. Considers waste streams specific to the organization and region, the general need to avoid pollution/ fouling the planet irrespective of direct effect on living organisms and applies best practices for hazardous waste.

Art work, cultural heritage object specific / professional parameters

G9 Material/product selection and application method

Considers the effect of combining the material/product and its application method within an approach/treatment for any change in potential impacts due to the specific combinations (e.g. solvent applied with either cotton swab, gel or tissue/preparing an enclosure with materials for eventual separation and re-use).

G10 Efficiency - Number of applications/consumption/quantities of materials/products used

Considers the quantity of material/product needed. Considers the amount used in a single application and the number of repeated applications required to achieve the desired result. Considers what can be reused and how much will be needed for the duration of the total process (hours, day, month or year).

G11 Longevity of result

Considers the lifetime of the treatment/result of the approach. Considers the durability/purity/quality of the materials/products added to the object within the approach/treatment. Considers the frequency of subsequent interventions/maintenance as a result of the approach (none, every year, 5 years, 10 years, > 10 years), and the type of maintenance that would be required (carbon-based, electrical (renewable, non-renewable), chemical, manual.)

G12 Accessibility – availability of approach/used materials/products

Considers the costs involved (qualitatively assessed by user) of the materials used in the approach/treatment, within the context of risk assessment and safe efficacy, Considers whether the materials are available as a commercial product for the user, whether they are already present (in the studio/lab/etc) or need to be purchased, and considers the transparency of material/product information.

G13 Accessibility – Ease of use and time

Considers the ease of using the treatment/approach, materials/products, considering the working properties and the time needed for testing the approach/materials/product, and the time needed for carrying out the treatment/approach. Considers the potential professional/long-term benefits of any new method/innovative approach.

G14 Quality/value impacts of result in meeting preservation goals

Considers the quality and value impact of the material/product, treatment/approach in meeting preservation goals, e.g. success of treatment/remedial action in preventing deterioration/increasing public accessibility.

Additional Background/FAQ section

Concept, Goal and Scope

- Conceptually aligned with a scientific attitude (care for empirical evidence, and willingness to change theory in the face of new empirical evidence), the definition and parameters aim to differentiate and broadly outline the unique characteristics of green conservation from a sustainability perspective.
- The definition and parameters are aspirational with the intention to guide clearer evaluations of green conservation in all aspects and disciplines within cultural heritage conservation, encouraging the use of reliable and comparable data where possible.
- It aligns with the circular economy.

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Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices

Work in progress definition / 31.01.25

How to Use/Implementation tips

- The parameters are intended to provide guidance in both theory and practice.
- 100 % green does not exist, and the parameters are not intended as an exhaustive list. One solution/approach will be greener with regards to some parameters, whilst another might be greener in others. There will always be a balancing aspect.
- The parameters can be considered in any order and depending on context. *An example would be examining different ways to condition enclosures (with an identical result) and considering the total energy implications of each.*
- The parameters can be considered in terms of only those decisions that are directly within the control of an individual professional or used to address the broadest aspects within a wider discussion involving multiple stakeholders. To support context specificity and agency, a weighting system to indicate big vs small impact items has not been applied.
- Further/future considerations can be added - if not specified here it is hoped/anticipated these can fall under one of the parameters.

Background/Frameworks

- Developed from a sustainability framework, combining LCA, LCC, S-LCA approaches and alignment with principles of green heritage science e.g. inherently non-harmful, maximization of (safe) efficiency etc.
- Where possible, internationally recognized frameworks, data and metrics can be applied - such as the Globally Harmonized System (e.g. in G1 and G2), LCA data (e.g. contributing in G1 through G7) and guidelines (e.g. BIZOT).
- Whilst certain quantitative frameworks can be applied to the parameters, other aspects can only be assessed qualitatively/comparatively and/or rely on context-specific primary data/inputs from the user.
- It is recognized that diverse frameworks of knowledge maybe further needed, with specifications and developments that respect the subjective nature of an artwork/cultural heritage's values, meaning and purpose.
- The parameters are grouped for clarity. Where certain effects/impacts could be theoretically considered in multiple parameters, an approach has been taken to avoid repetition and confusion by aiming to determine the **primary association** within the main impact categories specified e.g. *harmful impacts (toxicity and chemical hazards/risks) on non-human living organisms from disposal of a material are considered in G1 (which encompasses the entire life cycle). Other impacts that could be potentially linked, such as on biodiversity from the associated polluting waste for instance, would be subsequent/secondary knock-on effects.*

Disclaimer/Acknowledgements

It is acknowledged that the associated assessments are highly complex, and since not all future developments and socio-economic contexts can be foreseen, a timeless definition of green is impossible.

Further, continuing work

The definition and parameters form the base for the GoGreen Digital Support App (DSA) which is being created, and our continuing research aims to provide specific details on frameworks that could be applied in assessments. An FAQ section will be included to address concerns or disagreements raised, as well as tips and links for the future implementation of the definition in conservators' day-to-day work life.

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Appendix VII - GoGreen_definition and parameters_06_02_25

Defining Green for Conservation Decisions & Practices

Work in progress definition / 06.02.2025

Holistic Definition for Cultural Heritage Conservation

Conservation has a uniquely positive and powerful role to play in shaping a sustainable future: it preserves cultural heritage for current and future generations and supports economic and societal stability. Climate change and its destructive impacts endangers cultural heritage. So a vital part of cultural heritage conservation is assessing and adapting professional practices to help combat these foremost agents of change. Embedded within this sustainability context, green conservation prioritizes the environment, and human health and wellbeing, through holistic decision-making. Aligned with conservation ethics and values, it allows for future developments and considers the entirety of consequences within investigative, interventive and preventive practice. It involves a considered balancing of the impacts, before, during and after any decision or approach. Cultural heritage professionals should actively adopt a green conservation approach, with institutional support in accordance with the Economic, Social and Environmental pillars of sustainability.

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Green Parameters descriptors for green conservation (see website for details)

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	G13	Accessibility – Ease of use and time
	G14	Quality / value impacts of result in meeting preservation goals

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